

**Experiment Driven and user Experience Oriented Analytics for
Extremely Precise Outcomes and Decisions**

**D3.2 Constraint-aware ML and analytics
services**

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Abstract	This deliverable summarizes the research results related to the constraint-aware, adaptive, and scalable machine learning (ML) methods developed in the ExtremeXP. It first introduces novel ML algorithms that embed performance and physics-based constraints into loss functions—enhancing cybersecurity classification and flood prediction accuracy. It also presents a structure-constrained clustering method (UEC) and a meta-learning tool for automated model selection. It then explores online and continual learning for evolving data streams, and a lightweight deployment unit to enable scalable ML workflows across clusters and cloud platforms. Together, these innovations advance robust, efficient, and deployable ML systems.
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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
Ada-RDA	Adaptive Regularized Dual Averaging
ARC-LSTM	Auto-regressive Encoder-Decoder Conv LSTM architecture
AROW	Adaptive Regularization of Weights
BCE	Binary Cross Entropy
CA	Constraint-Aware
FN	False Negative
FNR	False Negative Rate
FP	False Positive
FPR	False Positive Rate
GLC	Gradient Learning Classifier
Max (max)	Maximum
Min (min)	Minimum
ML	Machine Learning
NN-Fbeta	Neural Network-Fbeta
NN-BCE	Neural Network-BCE
PA	Passive-Aggressive
PIML	Physics-Informed Machine Learning
RDA	Regularized Dual Averaging
TN	True Negative
TP	True Positive
SbC	Surrogate loss-based classification
SCW	Soft Confidence-Weighted
UEC	Unified Embedding and Clustering
WPA	Weighted Passive-Aggressive
HABR	Letter H before the algorithm denotes hybrid
CABR	Letter C before the algorithm denotes continual
OABR	Letter O before the algorithm denotes online
BABR	Letter B before the algorithm denotes batch

Executive Summary

This deliverable covers the research activities undertaken as part of Task 3.4, Task 3.5, and Task 3.6 within WP3. It mainly addresses and describes the following:

a. Constraint-aware ML algorithms (T3.4) (see Section 2):

Two types of constraints have been covered: (i) performance-related constraints and (ii) physics-driven constraints. The choice of such constraints was motivated by two use cases: UC2 (Cybersecurity) and UC1 (Flush flood). The core idea of the research is to explicitly embed constraints in the form of a loss term so that the models can be trained while aware of such constraints. The primary contributions of this work are threefold:

- Performance-related constraints (T3.4) (see Section 2.1): To tackle the pervasive issue of imbalanced data in cybersecurity - where the cost of false negatives (missed attacks) is extremely high, we developed many novel classification algorithms (see Table 1: List and nature of the contributions). By devising a variety of surrogate loss functions that directly optimize the trade-off between Precision and Recall, these models are designed to minimize both false positives and false negatives. The proposed algorithms were rigorously tested in batch settings on UC2 data.
- Physics-driven constraints (T3.4) (see Section 2.5): to address the need of UC1, we developed a novel physics-informed ML (PIML) model, integrating the fundamental laws of fluid dynamics (the Shallow Water Equations) directly into the loss function of a Conv LSTM neural network. This model forces the predictions to be physically plausible, improving accuracy and generalization. Initial results on sample flood data (UC1) confirm the model's ability to produce accurate water depth forecasts, demonstrating a promising direction for operational hazard response.
- Structure constraint in clustering (T3.4) (see Section 2.6): To enable high-quality clustering of high-dimensional data, we developed a new algorithm, called UEC, that treats embedding and clustering simultaneously to uncover data structure reliably by constraining manifold embedding through clustering. The constraint is expressed as a loss term imposed on the topology of the data. UEC was evaluated on several benchmark datasets showing great performance compared to the state-of-art competitors.

b. Model selection using meta-learning (T3.4) (see Section 3):

To accelerate the ML workflow, we developed a new meta-learning tool for automated model/algorithm selection. The tool offers the ability to collect data about ML experiments which consist of model, model configuration, and datasets. Given a new dataset for a new experiment, the tool locates the most similar datasets in the database and the corresponding best-performing algorithms that will be recommended for the new dataset. The proposed tool helps streamlining the model selection and computational efficiency (which could be seen as a constraint).

c. Online and continual learning (T3.5) (see Section 2.3)

The assumption here is that data comes over time and ML algorithms should be open-ended, able to learn sequentially and continuously. Here we explored standard online learning as well as task-incremental continual learning (specifically task-agnostic continual learning). The two scenarios have been explored through some of the proposed algorithms in (a) on UC2 data which is offered in the form of a set of tasks.

d. Scalable ML and data analytics workflow deployment on clusters/Clouds (T3.6) (Section 4):

The assumption here is that the data comes from various data owners may not be enabled to utilize the ExtremeXP framework. Primarily due to the necessity of data movement onto the platform for experimentation and usage of analytical tools. Here we propose a light-weight unit that can enable the usage of the experimentation framework to enable deployment that may not have been feasible previously. We primarily consider classification validated on UC2.

Overall, this deliverable has covered several aspects leading a good number of novel algorithms and methods that highlights the extensive research undertaken in T3.4, T3.5 and T3.6.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context of the work

The tasks covered by this deliverable are briefly described:

- **Task 3.4 (Opportunistic Constraint-Aware ML):** This task addresses the problem of learning while observing constraints put forward by users, which could be underlying data (data biases) used to train the models, pre-defined/known relationships by the users, established laws that govern the processes being learned, or even evaluation quality measures. The task also investigates algorithm and model selection to speed up the best fit-for-purpose models when new learning problem (with constraint or constraint free) is proposed by the user.
- **Task 3.5 (Continual Adaptation):** Complementing T3.4, this task investigates the adaptation of the proposed algorithms to new data. In particular, it focusses on online learning and task-agnostic continual learning (TACL) that is general enough to cover all needs of the use cases and the evolution of their targeted algorithms.
- **Task 3.6 (Model Deployment):** This task addresses the integration of the ExtremeXP experimentation with multiple cloud providers. We focus on the scenario of the distribution of data when the data owners store their data on multiple data servers. We focus also on the problem when using the ExtremeXP experimentation may not be fully possible due to data constraints. We provide a solution that can enable a fuller utilization of experimentations.

1.2 Overview of learning with constraints

Traditional machine learning (ML) models excel at optimizing a single, well-defined objective function, typically related to predictive accuracy (e.g., minimizing mean squared error or cross-entropy loss). However, real-world problems are rarely that simple. They are often governed by a rich set of explicit rules, physical laws, ethical guidelines, and operational requirements. Constraint-Aware Machine Learning (CAML) emerges as a critical paradigm to bridge this gap, embedding domain-specific knowledge and explicit constraints directly into the model's training and inference process. Instead of treating the learning algorithm as a black box that only learns from data, CAML enriches it with prior knowledge, leading to models that are not only accurate but also more robust, interpretable, fair, and physically plausible.

The review of the literature shows that there are various ways of imposing constraints on ML algorithms. Figure 1 highlights different types of constraints that can be algorithm specific as described in (Nanfack et al., 2022) relation to decision trees or can be algorithm independent. In this work we are interested in the latter. In the following we describe some of such constraints.

Figure 1: Constraint-aware learning

Attribute-Level Constraints: they aim to impose rules on the individual features or properties of the data and their relationship with the model's output. These are crucial for ensuring data integrity, fairness, and logical consistency and other types of constraints such as.

- a. Monotonicity Constraints: A common requirement in domains like finance (a higher credit score should not lead to a lower loan approval probability) or medicine is that the relationship between an input feature and the output is always non-decreasing or non-increasing. Traditional models like deep neural networks do not inherently guarantee this. Research in this area focuses on developing model architectures or regularization terms that enforce this property. Techniques range from specialized network architectures with positive weights to post-processing methods like isotonic regression. This ensures that the model's behaviour aligns with logical, real-world expectations.
- b. Fairness and Bias Constraints: A major focus of modern ML research is mitigating unwanted bias. Attribute-level fairness constraints are designed to ensure that a model's predictions are equitable across different demographic groups defined by sensitive attributes like race or gender. Foundational work has introduced concepts like "equality of opportunity," which requires that the true positive rate is equal across groups. These constraints are typically implemented by adding a regularization term to the loss function that penalizes disparities in model outcomes.
- c. Privacy Constraints: In domains handling sensitive data, privacy is a paramount constraint. Differential Privacy provides a formal framework for guaranteeing that the output of a model does not reveal sensitive information about any single individual in the training data. This is achieved by injecting calibrated noise into the learning process, constraining the amount of information that can be leaked.
- d. Data Movement Constraints: In domains handling sensitive data, the raw data is of the utmost importance. This means that the raw data cannot leave the storage premises. Meaning that any utilization of external compute for experimentation is infeasible. We will incorporate the usage of hidden functions. Hidden functions have the property that to any external member the function is unknown. There will be insufficient information to recreate the function to attack the data.

Instance-Level Constraints: These constraints focus on the relationships *between* individual data points. They are particularly powerful in semi-supervised or unsupervised learning settings where they can guide the model using a small amount of prior knowledge.

- a. Must-Link and Cannot-Link Constraints: This is the most classic example of instance-level constraints, particularly in clustering. A "must-link" constraint specifies that two data points must belong to the same cluster, while a "cannot-link" constraint dictates they must belong to different clusters. This allows a user to inject domain knowledge (e.g., "these two images are of the same person" or "this customer cannot be in the same segment as that one") to produce more meaningful and accurate clusters.

Structure-Level Constraints: These constraints pertain to the overall architecture, complexity, or functional form of the model itself. These are often used to ensure generalization, physical consistency, and efficiency.

- a. Algorithmic Complexity Constraints: A fundamental constraint in all of ML is managing model complexity to avoid overfitting. This is often achieved through regularisation techniques, which are a form of structural constraint. For example, L1 (Lasso) and L2 (Ridge) regularization constrain the magnitude of model weights. In deep learning, dropout acts as a powerful structural regularizer by randomly setting a fraction of neuron activations to zero during training, constraining the network from becoming overly reliant on any single feature path.
- b. Physics-Informed Constraints: A rapidly growing frontier is *Physics-Informed Machine Learning (PIML)*, where the governing laws of a system, typically expressed as partial differential equations (PDEs), are embedded as a soft constraint in the model's loss function. Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) are trained to simultaneously minimize

the error against observed data points and the residual of the governing PDEs. This ensures that the model's predictions are not only data-driven but also physically consistent, which is invaluable in scientific and engineering applications where data may be sparse, but the underlying physics is well understood.

Recently the concept of *knowledge-informed machine learning* has been proposed as a generalisation of all possible constraints, revolving around the integration of explicit prior knowledge into ML algorithms. Click or tap here to enter text. such generalisation is portrayed in Figure 2.

A constraint on a **loss function** is the primary **implementation mechanism** used to enforce what is most often a **Structure-Level Constraint**. In our work by adding a constraint to the loss function, we define a specific goal or objective.

Figure 2: Integration of various types of knowledge into ML

1.3 Scope of the Contributions

The execution of T3.4 and T4.5 was mostly driven by the needs of UC1 and UC2. The team engaged mostly with UC2 which offer the interesting problem of data imbalance and the high rate of false positives and false negatives when using general ML algorithms, which refers to performance constraints. UC1 was addressed from the physics constraint related to flow modelling. T3.5 is mostly extension of T3.4 to adapt the algorithms developed in T3.4 to online and continual algorithms. At this stage not all algorithms have their online or task-agnostic continual learning counterpart. Investigations are still underway.

Table 1: List and nature of the contributions summarises the set of contributions developed as part of Task 3.4, Task 3.5, and Task 3.6 within WP3.

Task	Nature of the contribution	Constraint type	Primary validation target	Algorithms
T3.4	Constraint-aware ML algorithms	Performance-related constraints	UC2	SbC CbC PA WPA AROW CW RDA Ada-RDA GLC

		Physics-driven constraints	UC1	ARC-LSTM
		Structure-related constraints	Public data	UEC
	Model selection using meta-learning	Fitness, Efficiency, Performance	Independent	Standalone tool
T3.5	Online and continual learning (task-agnostic continual learning)	Performance-related constraints	UC2	Online PA Continual PA Online WPA Continual WPA Online AROW Continual AROW Online CW Continual CW Online RDA Continual RDA Online Ada-RDA Online GLC Continual GLC
T3.6	Deployment of Scalable ML and data analytics workflow	Multi-Platform Model Deployment	UC2	Encoder-Decoder-ML

Table 1: List and nature of the contributions

In a nutshell, we tried to cover both supervised and unsupervised learning while coping with various constraints about False Positives (FP) and False Negatives (FN) as well as flow modelling. Several algorithms have been developed:

- Supervised learning
 - *Offline:*
 - Offline surrogate loss-based classification (SbC)
 - Offline cost-based classification (CbC)
 - Offline passive-aggressive learning (PA)
 - Offline weighted passive aggressive learning (WPA)
 - Offline gradient learning classifier (GLC)
 - Offline adaptive regularization of weight vectors (AROW)
 - Offline regularized dual averaging (RDA)
 - Offline soft confidence weighted (SCW)
 - Offline adaptive regularized dual averaging (Ada-RDA)
 - Physics-Informed Auto-regressive Encoder-Decoder Conv LSTM (ARC-LSTM)
 - *Online and continual:*
 - Continual gradient learning classifier (CGLC)
 - Continual perceptron learning classifier (CP)
 - Continual passive aggressive learning classifier (CPA)
 - Continual weighted passive aggressive learning classifier (CWPA)
 - Continual adaptive regularization of weight vectors (CAROW)
 - Continual regularized dual averaging (CRDA)
 - Continual soft confidence weighted (CSCW)
 - Continual adaptive regularised dual averaging (Cada-RDA)
 - Online gradient learning classifier (OGLC)
 - Online weighted passive aggressive learning (OWPA)
- Unsupervised learning

- Unified embedding and clustering (UEC)
- Meta Learning for automated model/algorithm selection. This tool recommends the most promising algorithms for a new dataset by analysing its similarity to past experiments, thereby streamlining model selection, and improving computational efficiency (which could be seen as a constraint).

The core concept of T3.4 and T3.5 is constraint-aware learning and therefore much of the work was directed towards developing the algorithms listed above, taking care of some constraints as described earlier. To summarize such contributions, we provide details in Table 2: Summary of Algorithms which presents a summary of the algorithms along with the constraints covered by each algorithm. These will be individually discussed in the next sections. The source code for all algorithms is available in python on GitHub¹.

Algorithm	Objective	Constraint	Offline	Continual	Online
SbC	To discourage false positives (false alarm)	FN threshold	Contribution	-	-
CbC	Minimise the expected cost of the decisions the classifier makes	Error cost ratio	Contribution	-	-
PA	To fix any error with the smallest change to current knowledge (weights).	Min (FP, FN)	Contribution	Contribution	In literature
WPA	To fix any error with the smaller (change than PA) to current knowledge (weights).	Min (FP, FN)	Contribution	Contribution	Contribution
GLC	To be as accurate as possible and as flexible as possible while keeping it simple.	$\text{Max}((\text{TP}+\text{TN})/(\text{TP}+\text{TN}+\text{FP}+\text{FN}))$	Contribution	Contribution	Contribution
AROW	To learn from an error without forgetting everything else.	Min (FP, FN)	Contribution	Contribution	In literature
RDA	To be accurate while keeping it simple.	Min (FP, FN)	Contribution	Contribution	In literature
SCW	To update belief system such that every decision is made with statistical confidence	Min (Pr(FP), Pr(FN))	Contribution	Contribution	In literature
Ada-RDA	To be accurate and simple (like RDA) but use features that have proven to be very helpful in the past.	Min (FP, FN)	Contribution	Contribution	In literature

Table 2: Summary of Algorithms

On the other hand, T3.6 aims at enabling scalable deployment and usage of the ExtremeXP framework. We want to scale to multiple data sources to perform experiments upon. The data can be separated based on various constraints. We will thus perform our research on the models and model architectures that can allow us to full integrate the data under these constraints. The result of our contribution will allow users with constrained data settings to be able to train machine learning models. The models may not be just for the task, but also to be able to utilize the other analytical tools. Such as the usage of data augmentation in conjunction with the training of the models.

¹ [Constraint-aware ML · GitLab](#)

2 Description of the Algorithms

This section will overview briefly all algorithms developed, categorised according to the learning paradigms. The presentation of each algorithm covers the type of constraint considered, brief formulation of the approach as well as the self-explanatory pseudo-code for the sake of completeness.

2.1 Offline learning

2.1.1 Surrogate-loss based Classification Algorithm

a) Constraint covered

The objective is to minimize the false positive rate (FPR), which is defined as:

$$FPR = \frac{FP}{TN + FP}$$

This optimization is subject to a constraint on the false negative rate (FNR), ensuring it does not exceed a threshold FN rate (10% for this study), formally expressed as:

$$\frac{FN}{TP + FN} < fn_{rate}$$

This constraint limits the proportion of actual positive cases that can be misclassified as negative, preserving model sensitivity. The formulation balances the trade-off between reducing false positives and maintaining an acceptable level of false negatives, as determined by the defined threshold.

b) Brief presentation of the approach

It is observed that performance (aiming at reducing FPs and FNs) decreases when the data is imbalanced. To address this, we adopt and extend a surrogate loss function inspired by recent work on F_β optimization (Lee et al., 2021). Class-balanced loss functions based on inverse class frequencies have shown promise (Wang et al., 2017; Cui et al., 2019), but traditional metric-optimization methods struggle with deep networks (Joachims, 2005; Kar et al., 2014; Narasimhan et al., 2015; Sanyal et al., 2018). Our proposed loss is differentiable, scalable, and aligned with F_β gradients for improved performance. The formulation addresses the non-differentiability of the F_β score by introducing a smooth surrogate loss that enables direct optimization in gradient-based learning. We formulate our F_β loss function by incorporating two additional weighting terms—one for FPs and one for FNs as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 TP(\theta) &= \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \hat{y}_i, & TN(\theta) &= \sum_{i=1}^n (1 - y_i)(1 - \hat{y}_i) \\
 FP(\theta) &= \sum_{i=1}^n (1 - y_i) \hat{y}_i, & FN(\theta) &= \sum_{i=1}^n y_i(1 - \hat{y}_i) \\
 Loss = \widetilde{F}_\beta &= \frac{(1 + \beta^2) \cdot TP}{\beta^2 + \theta + TP - \theta \cdot TN + penalty_{fp}} + penalty_{fn} \\
 Penalty_{FP} &= weight_{FP} \times FP \\
 Penalty_{FN} &= \max(0, P - FixedFN)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$FixedFN = Weight_{FN} \times P$$

$$\theta = \frac{p}{1-p}; \quad \text{where } p \text{ represents the number of positive samples in the training data}$$

The presented loss function was integrated in a deep net as shown in Figure 3, where SbC is compared against balancing techniques (oversampling, under sampling and hybrid) as well as against the deep net with the standard BCE loss.

Figure 3: SbC architecture

c) Steps of the Algorithm

Require:

True labels $\mathbf{y}_{\text{true}} \in \{0, 1\}^n$
Predicted probabilities $\mathbf{y}_{\text{pred}} \in [0, 1]^n$
F-beta parameter $\beta > 0$
Binarization threshold $\tau \in [0, 1]$
False Positive weight $w_{FP} \geq 0$
False Negative weight $w_{FN} \geq 0$

```

1:  $P \leftarrow \sum \mathbf{y}_{\text{true}}$                                 ▷ Total number of positive samples
2:  $N \leftarrow n - P$                                     ▷ Total number of negative samples
3:  $\theta \leftarrow N/P$                                     ▷ Ratio of negative to positive samples
4:  $\hat{\mathbf{y}} \leftarrow (\mathbf{y}_{\text{pred}} > \tau)$                 ▷ Binarize predictions to 0 or 1
                                                    ▷ The following are weighted rates, not standard TP/TN/FP rates

5:  $TP_w \leftarrow \frac{\sum(\hat{\mathbf{y}} \odot \mathbf{y}_{\text{true}} \odot \mathbf{y}_{\text{pred}})}{P}$ 
6:  $TN_w \leftarrow \frac{\sum((1-\hat{\mathbf{y}}) \odot (1-\mathbf{y}_{\text{true}}) \odot (1-\mathbf{y}_{\text{pred}}))}{N}$ 
7:  $FP_w \leftarrow \frac{\sum(\hat{\mathbf{y}} \odot (1-\mathbf{y}_{\text{true}}) \odot \mathbf{y}_{\text{pred}})}{N}$                 ▷ Note: Normalized by N (negatives)

8:  $P_{FP} \leftarrow w_{FP} \cdot FP_w$                                 ▷ Calculate the FP penalty term
9:  $C_{FN} \leftarrow w_{FN} \cdot P$                                 ▷ Calculate the FN constraint budget

10:                                                    ▷ Calculate the base F-beta score with the weighted rates and FP penalty
11:  $f_\beta \leftarrow \frac{(1+\beta^2) \cdot TP_w}{\beta^2 + \theta + TP_w - \theta \cdot TN_w + P_{FP}}$ 

12:                                                    ▷ Apply the penalty for violating the False Negative constraint
13:  $f_\beta \leftarrow f_\beta + \max(0, \text{FN.count} - C_{FN})$                 ▷ Assuming a penalty on exceeding FN budget

14: return  $-f_\beta$                                 ▷ Return negative score for minimization by an optimizer

```

Figure 4: SbC

2.1.2 Cost-based learning Classification Algorithm

a) Constraint covered

When a mistake is made, the consequences of different types of error can vary arbitrarily. When these consequences can be quantified into a single number which might represent financial or productivity losses, we arrive at the notion of cost. For a fixed choice of user requirements this provides an intuitive single way of ranking the performance of models.

Probabilistically, one is really looking to minimise the expected cost of each decision made, which for binary classification can be written

$$E(\text{cost}) = E(\text{cost of a FP}) * P(\text{FP}) + E(\text{cost of a FN}) * P(\text{FN})$$

If a user has some idea of the distribution of the costs of different error types, they can train and benchmark a neural network according to these requirements. Since a neural network returns a float, a classification made by a user depends on a cutoff that they may vary depending on their situation. If they can provide distributions for the costs of each error type, the quantity that a model should minimise is given by a simple integral formula (Komisarenko & Kull, 2025).

Results presented here focus on minimising cost subject to the constraint that a false negative costs a fixed multiple of a false positive. We investigate training using a simple generalisation of binary cross entropy (BCE) and L_p loss functions.

b) Brief presentation of the approach

Let $\sigma(x)$ denote the sigmoid function. Let + and – denote positive and negative target class labels, respectively. Define $L(a,b; prediction, target)$ piecewise as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} L(0, b; prediction, +) &= \log(\sigma(prediction)) && \text{for } b \geq 0, \\ L(a, b; prediction, +) &= \frac{1 - \sigma(prediction)^a}{a} && \text{for } a > 0 \text{ and } b \geq 0, \\ L(a, 0; prediction, -) &= \log(\sigma(-prediction)) && \text{for } a \geq 0, \text{ and} \\ L(a, b; prediction, -) &= \frac{1 - \sigma(-prediction)^b}{b} && \text{for } b > 0 \text{ and } a \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

When $a = b = 0$ we recover the BCE loss, and $a = b$ is effectively an L_p loss. Differing values of a and b , however, correspond to differing tail risks associated with the different error types. Accordingly, we sought to test the hypothesis that using such values for a and b might be beneficial when there is a large discrepancy in the costs.

To align results with other tables presented here, we provide the results of using these models at fixed cost ratios – for example, a cost ratio of 10 means that a false negative is ten times as costly as a false positive. Depending on the precise value of this trade-off, the numbers of one type of error grow as the other rate shrinks.

In the context of cybersecurity threat detection, one may consider the cost ratio to be a parameter that defines a filter’s permissiveness – the more serious the risks of a false negative are, the more legitimate traffic gets blocked.

c) Steps of the Algorithm

This family of loss functions is applicable to traditional offline model training. Following the experimental approach of the original paper which introduced rbd24 (Calvo et al. 2025) users were split 60:20:20 into training, validation, and test datasets. Results provided show the test performance for those parameters that performed best on the validation dataset. The results reported are for the case where a false negative is 16 times as costly as a false positive. The result is a classifier with low tolerance for potentially malicious traffic. In the results provided here, nearly all malicious traffic is correctly identified at the cost of also blocking the bulk of the legitimate traffic. Experiments were conducted only on NonEnc_desktop and P2P_desktop, since the imbalance was consistent between the different datasets when splitting by user.

The training dataset was resampled according to each of the schemes under evaluation. These were: No resampling, NearMiss, SMOTEENN, ADASYN, SMOTE and SMOTETomek.

The model weights were initialised and trained using the Flax framework. This standard approach involves repeatedly shuffling and batching the training dataset, then iterating through the batches, applying a single Adam step with a learning rate of 0.001 to the weights for each one. After training, a NN returns a prediction which is float valued. The training data was then used to select an optimal cutoff for each cost ratio under consideration, where a float output is a positive prediction if its value is above that cutoff.

The randomly-constrained-learning library used to generate these results consists of data loading helpers, a caching resampling class interface, and a neural network pipeline class interface. The code is documented, and example notebooks are provided to aid experimental repeatability.

This algorithm is still under being fine-tuned and thoroughly evaluated.

2.1.3 Online To Batch Classification Algorithms

The CAML algorithms described in the following subsection are:

- Offline passive-aggressive learning (PA)
- Offline weighted passive aggressive learning (WPA)
- Offline gradient learning classifier (GLC)
- Offline adaptive regularization of weight vectors (AROW)
- Offline regularized dual averaging (RDA)
- Offline soft confidence weighted (SCW)
- Offline adaptive regularized dual averaging (Ada-RDA)

To tackle both the requirements of T3.4 and T3.5 we decided to design algorithms that are online by design and then run them differently. According to T3.4 (offline setting), we will adapt them to offline/batch setting as explained in the protocol illustrated in Figure 5. In a nutshell, to create the batch version, we introduce stochasticity by making multiple passes and shuffling the training data on each pass assuming that data is i.i.d or the training data and test data are from the same distribution. The idea is to shuffle the data and, on each shuffle, compute some pre-defined measure (in this study F-beta). The protocol is theoretically sound, justified by a theorem linking the regret and convergence.

```

Input: Training data  $D_{\text{train}} = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ ,
       Validation data  $D_{\text{val}}$ ,
       algorithm denoted by  $ALG$ , Number of epochs  $E$ ,
       Measure (to optimise)

(1) Initialize parameters  $\theta_1$  from  $ALG$ 
(2) Initialize best score  $s_{\text{OPT}} \leftarrow -1.0$ 
(3) Initialize OPT parameters  $\theta_{\text{OPT}} \leftarrow \theta_1$ 

FOR  $e = 1, 2, \dots, E$ 
  (A) // Introduce stochasticity by shuffling
       $D'_{\text{train}} \leftarrow \text{Shuffle}(D_{\text{train}})$ 

  (B) // Train on shuffled data
       $\theta \leftarrow \theta^{(e-1)}$  // Start from previous epoch's weights
      FOR each instance  $(x_i, y_i)$  in  $D'_{\text{train}}$ 
         $\theta \leftarrow \text{UpdateRule}(\theta, x_i, y_i)$ 
      END FOR
       $\theta^{(e)} \leftarrow \theta$  // Store final weights for this epoch

  (C) // Evaluate on validation set
       $Y_{\text{pred}} \leftarrow \text{Predict}(ALG, D_{\text{val}}, \theta^{(e)})$ 
       $s_{\text{current}} \leftarrow \text{Measure}(Y_{\text{val}}, Y_{\text{pred}})$ 

  (D) // Save the OPT
      IF  $s_{\text{current}} > s_{\text{OPT}}$ 
         $s_{\text{OPT}} \leftarrow s_{\text{current}}$ 
         $\theta_{\text{OPT}} \leftarrow \theta^{(e)}$ 
      END IF
END FOR

Return  $\theta_{\text{OPT}}$ 

```

Figure 5: Online to batch protocol

2.1.3.1 Passive-Aggressive Learning Algorithm

a) Constraint covered

The constraint of $\max\{0, 1 - y\} = 0$ intuitive interpretation is $\min(FP, FN)$. Hinge Loss is a much stronger condition. It does not just try to minimize errors; it tries to build a maximally robust classifier by enforcing a margin of safety. Here y denotes the ground truth.

b) Brief presentation of the approach

The Passive-Aggressive learning algorithm is studied in online setting (Crammer et al., 2006a). PA algorithm analytically calculates the exact, minimal update required to correct its mistake on the current sample. The algorithm considers the following optimisation problem:

$$w_{t+1} = \operatorname{argmin} \frac{1}{2} \|w - w_t\|^2 \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \ell(w; (x_t, y_t)) = 0$$

Geometrically, w_{t+1} is set to be the projection of w_t onto the half-space of vectors which attain a hinge-loss of zero on the current example. The resulting algorithm is passive whenever the hinge-loss is zero, that is $w_{t+1} = w_t$ whenever $\ell_t = 0$. In contrast, on those rounds where the loss is positive, the algorithm aggressively forces w_{t+1} to satisfy the constraint $\ell(w_{t+1}; (x_t, y_t)) = 0$ regardless of the step-size required. Thus, the name Passive-Aggressive or PA for short. The solution to the above is as follows:

$$w_{t+1} = w_t + \tau_t y_t x_t \quad \text{where} \quad \tau = \frac{\ell_t}{\|x_t\|^2}$$

The authors presented the algorithm in online setup our contribution is in translating the operation in batch setting.

c) Steps of the Algorithm

```

1: Initialize:  $w \leftarrow 0$ 
2: for each training example  $(x_i, y_i)$  do
3:                                      $\triangleright$  Predict label
4:    $\hat{y}_i \leftarrow \operatorname{sign}(\langle w, x_i \rangle)$ 
5:                                      $\triangleright$  Calculate hinge loss
6:    $\ell_i \leftarrow \max(0, 1 - y_i \hat{y}_i)$ 
7:                                      $\triangleright$  Calculate learning rate  $\tau_i$ 
8:    $\tau_i \leftarrow \frac{\ell_i}{\|x_i\|_2^2 + \epsilon}$ 
9:                                      $\triangleright$  Update weight vector
10:   $w \leftarrow w + \tau_i y_i x_i$ 
11: end for

```

Figure 6:PA steps

2.1.3.2 Weighted Passive-Aggressive Learning Algorithm

a) Constraint covered

The constraint of $\max\{0, 1 - y\} = 0$ intuitive interpretation is $\min(FP, FN)$. Hinge Loss is a much stronger condition. It does not just try to minimize errors; it tries to build a maximally robust classifier by enforcing a margin of safety. Here y denotes the ground truth.

b) Brief presentation of the approach

We propose a modification to PA algorithm to have better initialisation. Instead of using the previous weight vector w_{t+1} in the optimisation problem of PA, we use \tilde{w}_t , to scale the weights in two steps.

$$w_{t+1} = \operatorname{argmin} \frac{1}{2} \|w - \tilde{w}_t\|^2 \quad \text{s.t. } \ell_t(w) = 0$$

Where $\tilde{w}_t = \sum \beta_s w_s$ and β_s is the coefficient of w_s with $\sum \beta_s = 1$. The solution to the above is as follows:

$$w_{t+1} = \tilde{w}_t + \alpha_t \frac{\ell(\tilde{w}_t)}{\|x\|^2}$$

Where $\ell_t(\tilde{w}_t) = \max\{0, 1 - y_t(\tilde{w}_t, x_t)\}$. This step employs an aggressive update strategy by modifying the previous weights by as much as necessary to satisfy the constraint imposed. In the second step following update is performed:

$$\tilde{w}_{t+1} = (1 - \rho_{t+1})\tilde{w}_t + \rho_{t+1}w_{t+1}$$

The parameter $\rho \in (0,1]$.

In scenario where the scaling of weights by rho does not influence the sign of the prediction PA, WPA will give the same result. The constraints are accommodated in the same way as in PA.

c) Steps of the Algorithm

- 1: Input: Hyperparameter $C > 0$, Smoothing factor $0 < \rho \leq 1$
- 2: Initialise $w_1 = (0, \dots, 0)^\top$.
- 3: **for** $t = 1, 2, \dots$ **do**
- 4: Receive instance $x_t \in \mathbb{R}^n$
- 5: Predict label $\hat{y}_t = \operatorname{sign}(\tilde{w}_t^\top x_t)$
- 6: Receive correct label $y_t \in \{-1, 1\}$
- 7: Suffer loss $\tilde{\ell}_t = \max\{0, 1 - y_t(\tilde{w}_t^\top x_t)\}$
- 8: Update parameter α_t :

$$\alpha_t = \frac{\ell_t(\tilde{w}_t)}{\|x_t\|^2}$$

- 9: Update with weighted moving average:

$$\tilde{w}_{t+1} = \tilde{w}_t + \rho_{t+1}\alpha_t y_t x_t$$

- 10: **end for**

Figure 7: WAPA steps

2.1.3.3 Adaptive Regularization of Weights Algorithm

a) Constraint covered

The constraint of $\max\{0, 1 - y\} = 0$ intuitive interpretation is $\min(FP, FN)$. Hinge Loss is a much stronger condition. It does not just try to minimize errors; it tries to build a maximally robust classifier by enforcing a margin of safety. Here y denotes the ground truth.

b) Brief presentation of the approach

The adaptive regularisation of weights or better known as AROW is proposed in online setting by Crammer et al., 2009. The algorithm considers the following problem:

$$C(\mu, \Sigma) = D_{KL}(N(\mu, \Sigma) || N(\mu_{t-1}, \Sigma_{t-1})) + \lambda_1 \ell_{h^2}(y_t, \mu' x_t) + \lambda_2 x_t' \Sigma x_t$$

Where $\ell_t(y_t, \mu' x_t) = (\max\{0, 1 - y_t(\mu' x_t)\})^2$, λ_1 & $\lambda_2 > 0$. To solve the above KL is written explicitly in the following manner.

$$C(\mu, \Sigma) = \underset{\mu, \Sigma}{\operatorname{argmin}} \frac{1}{2} \log \left(\frac{\det \Sigma_{t-1}}{\det \Sigma} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{Tr}(\Sigma_{t-1}^{-1} \Sigma) + \frac{1}{2} (\mu_{t-1} - \mu)' \Sigma_{t-1}^{-1} (\mu_{t-1} - \mu) - \frac{d}{2} + \frac{1}{2r} \ell_{h^2}(y_t, \mu' x_t) + \frac{1}{2r} x_t' \Sigma x_t$$

The above requires updates of the two terms μ and Σ . For details on the update equations please see discussion around equation (6) and equation (7) in (Cramer et al., 2009).

The authors presented the algorithm in online setup our contribution is in translating the operation in batch setting.

c) Steps of the algorithm

Require: Data examples (x_t, y_t) , where $x_t \in \mathbb{R}^d, y_t \in \{-1, +1\}$

Require: Regularization parameter $r > 0$

1: **Initialize:**

2: Mean vector (weights) $\mu \leftarrow \mathbf{0} \in \mathbb{R}^d$

3: Covariance matrix $\Sigma \leftarrow \mathbf{I} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$

4: **for each incoming example (x_t, y_t) do**

5: Calculate loss $\ell_t \leftarrow \max(0, 1 - y_t(\mu' x_t))$

6: **if $\ell_t > 0$ then**

▷ Only update if a margin error occurs

7: Calculate confidence $v_t \leftarrow x_t' \Sigma x_t$

8:

▷ Calculate update coefficients

9: $\beta_t \leftarrow \frac{1}{v_t + r}$

10: $\alpha_t \leftarrow \ell_t \cdot \beta_t$

11:

▷ Update the mean vector and covariance matrix

12: $\mu \leftarrow \mu + \alpha_t y_t \Sigma x_t$

13: $\Sigma \leftarrow \Sigma - \beta_t \Sigma x_t x_t' \Sigma$

Figure 8: AROW steps

2.1.3.4 Regularization Dual Averaging algorithm

a) Constraint covered

The constraint of $\max\{0, 1 - y\} = 0$ intuitive interpretation is $\min(FP, FN)$. Hinge Loss is a much stronger condition. It does not just try to minimize errors; it tries to build a maximally robust classifier by enforcing a margin of safety. Here y denotes the ground truth.

b) Brief presentation of the approach

The algorithm is proposed in stochastic and in online setting (Xiao, 2010). The algorithm's objective is as follows:

$$w_{t+1} = \underset{w}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\{ g_t' w + \psi(w) + \frac{\beta_t}{t} h(w) \right\}$$

Where g_t is the average sub gradient, ψ is the convex set of minimisers. The algorithm imposes following restrictions on closed convex loss functions:

$$h(\alpha w + (1 - \alpha)u) \leq \alpha h(w) + (1 - \alpha)h(u) - \frac{\sigma}{2}\alpha(1 - \alpha)\|w - u\|^2,$$

for all $w, u \in \text{dom } h$, $\alpha > 0$ & $\sigma > 0$, is the modulus of strong convexity. Also, β_t is a pre-determined nonnegative and nondecreasing sequence.

The authors presented the algorithm in online setup our contribution is in translating the operation in batch setting.

c) Steps of the algorithm

Require: Data (x_t, y_t) , $\lambda > 0$, $\gamma > 0$

```

1: Initialize:
2: Weights  $w \leftarrow \mathbf{0} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ 
3: Averaged subgradients  $\bar{g} \leftarrow \mathbf{0} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ 
4: Time step  $t \leftarrow 0$ 

5: for each incoming example  $(x_t, y_t)$  do
6:    $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
7:   Calculate loss  $\ell_t \leftarrow \max(0, 1 - y_t(w^T x_t))$ 
8:
9:   if  $\ell_t > 0$  then
10:     $g_t \leftarrow -y_t x_t$ 
11:   else
12:     $g_t \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$ 

13:                                     ▷ Update the averaged subgradient
14:    $\bar{g} \leftarrow \frac{t-1}{t}\bar{g} + \frac{1}{t}g_t$ 

15:                                     ▷ Update weights component-wise based on the average gradient
16:   for  $j = 1$  to  $d$  do
17:     $w_j \leftarrow \begin{cases} -\frac{\sqrt{t}}{\gamma}(g_j - \lambda \cdot \text{sgn}(g_j)) & \text{if } |g_j| > \lambda \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$ 

```

Figure 9: RDA steps

2.1.3.5 Adaptive Regularized Dual Averaging Algorithm

a) Constraint covered

The constraint of $\max\{0, 1 - y\} = 0$ intuitive interpretation is $\min(FP, FN)$. Hinge Loss is a much stronger condition. It does not just try to minimize errors; it tries to build a maximally robust classifier by enforcing a margin of safety. Here y denotes the ground truth.

b) Brief presentation of the approach

Duchi et al., 2011 change proximal function to achieve performance guarantees which are competitive with the best proximal term found in hindsight. The idea is to optimise the proximal and composite terms via sub-gradient and mirror descent:

$$w_{t+1} = \underset{w}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\{ \eta \left(\frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=1}^T g'_\tau w_\tau \right) + \eta \phi(w) + \frac{1}{t} \psi_t(w) \right\}$$

Where g_t is the sub gradient, ψ is strongly convex and monotonically non-decreasing, ϕ is strong convex function and regularizes the complexity of w . The above update is referred to as proximal term. The composite term is as follows:

$$w_{t+1} = \operatorname{argmin}\{\eta(g'_t w) + \eta\phi(w) + B_{\psi_t}(w, w_t)\}$$

Where g_t is the sub gradient, $\eta > 0$ is the learning rate and B_{ψ_t} is Bregman divergence associated with a strongly convex and differentiable function ψ at time t .

The authors presented the algorithm in online setup our contribution is in translating the operation in batch setting.

c) Steps of the algorithm

Require: Data (x_t, y_t) , $\lambda > 0$, learning rate $\eta > 0$, smoothing term $\delta > 0$

```

1: Initialize:
2: Weights  $w \leftarrow \mathbf{0} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ 
3: Averaged subgradients  $\bar{g} \leftarrow \mathbf{0} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ 
4: Sum of squared subgradients  $G \leftarrow \mathbf{0} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ 
5: Time step  $t \leftarrow 0$ 

6: for each incoming example  $(x_t, y_t)$  do
7:    $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
8:   Calculate loss  $\ell_t \leftarrow \max(0, 1 - y_t(w^T x_t))$ 
9:
10:  if  $\ell_t > 0$  then
11:     $g_t \leftarrow -y_t x_t$ 
12:  else
13:     $g_t \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$ 

14:                                     ▷ Update gradient statistics
15:    $\bar{g} \leftarrow \frac{t-1}{t} \bar{g} + \frac{1}{t} g_t$ 
16:    $G \leftarrow G + g_t \odot g_t$                                      ▷  $\odot$  is element-wise product

17:                                     ▷ Update weights component-wise
18:    $H_t \leftarrow \delta + \sqrt{G}$                                      ▷  $\sqrt{\cdot}$  is element-wise
19:   for  $j = 1$  to  $d$  do
20:      $w_j \leftarrow \begin{cases} -\operatorname{sgn}(\bar{g}_j) \frac{\eta \ell_t}{H_{t,j}} (|\bar{g}_j| - \lambda) & \text{if } |\bar{g}_j| > \lambda \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$ 

```

Figure 10: Ada-RDA steps

2.1.3.6 Soft Confidence Weighted Algorithm

a) Constraint covered

The loss function $\max(0, \phi(\sqrt{x_t \Sigma x_t} - y_t \mu' x_t)) = 0$ satisfies the probability constraint of $y_t(\mu' x_t) \geq \phi(\sqrt{x_t \Sigma x_t})$ and $\min(\operatorname{Pr}(FP), \operatorname{Pr}(F))$ can be thought of an intuitive explanation. Here y denotes the ground truth, x is the input, Σ is variance-covariance matrix and $\phi = \Phi^{-1}(\eta)$.

b) Brief presentation of the approach

The idea of softening the aggressiveness is inspired by PA in SCW. In (J. Wang et al., 2016a) w denotes the weight vector and is assumed to follow a Gaussian distribution with mean vector μ and covariance Σ . The objective of soft-margin classifier is as follows:

$$(\mu_{(t+1)}, \Sigma_{(t+1)}) = \operatorname{argmin} D_{KL}(N(\mu, \Sigma) || N(\mu_t, \Sigma_t)) + C \ell^\wedge \phi(N(\mu, \Sigma); (x_t, y))$$

The closed form solution to the above is as follows:

$$\mu_{t+1} = \Sigma_t - \beta_t \Sigma_t x_t' x_t \Sigma_t$$

The authors presented the algorithm in online setup our contribution is in translating the operation in batch setting. The updating coefficients are:

$$\alpha_t = \min \left\{ C, \max \left\{ 0, \frac{1}{(v_t \zeta) \left(-m_t \psi + \sqrt{\left(m_t^2 \frac{\phi^4}{4} + v_t \phi^2 \zeta \right)} \right)} \right\} \right\}$$

$$\beta_t = \frac{\alpha_t \phi}{\sqrt{u_t} + v_t \alpha_t \phi}$$

where $u_t = 1/4(-\alpha_t v_t \phi + \sqrt{(\alpha_t^2 v_t^2 + 4v_t)^2})$, $v_t = x_t' \Sigma_t x_t$, $m_t = y_t(\mu_t' x_t)$, $\phi = \Phi^{-1}(\eta)$, $\psi = 1 + \frac{\phi^2}{2}$ and $\zeta = 1 + \phi^2$.

c) Steps of the algorithm

Require: Data (x_t, y_t) , confidence $\eta \in (0, 1)$, aggressiveness $C > 0$

1: **Initialize:**

2: Mean vector (weights) $\mu \leftarrow \mathbf{0} \in \mathbb{R}^d$

3: Covariance matrix $\Sigma \leftarrow \mathbf{I} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$

4: Confidence parameter $\phi \leftarrow \Phi^{-1}(\eta)$

▷ Φ^{-1} is the inverse standard normal CDF

5: **for** each incoming example (x_t, y_t) **do**

6: Calculate margin $m_t \leftarrow y_t(\mu^T x_t)$

7: Calculate confidence $v_t \leftarrow x_t^T \Sigma x_t$

8: Calculate loss $\ell_t \leftarrow \max(0, \phi \sqrt{v_t} - m_t)$

9: **if** $\ell_t > 0$ **then**

10:

$$\xi_t \leftarrow 1 + \phi^2$$

11:

$$\psi_t \leftarrow 1 + \phi^2/2$$

12:

$$\zeta_t \leftarrow m_t^2 \phi^4/4 + v_t \phi^2 \xi_t$$

13:

$$\alpha_t \leftarrow \min \left(C, \max \left(0, \frac{-m_t \psi_t + \sqrt{\zeta_t}}{v_t \xi_t} \right) \right)$$

14:

15:

16:

$$u_t \leftarrow \frac{1}{4} \left(-\alpha_t v_t \phi + \sqrt{\alpha_t^2 v_t^2 \phi^2 + 4v_t} \right)^2$$

17:

$$\beta_t \leftarrow \frac{\alpha_t \phi}{\sqrt{u_t} + v_t \alpha_t \phi}$$

18:

19:

$$\mu \leftarrow \mu + \alpha_t y_t \Sigma x_t$$

20:

$$\Sigma \leftarrow \Sigma - \beta_t \Sigma x_t x_t^T \Sigma$$

▷ Calculate update coefficient α_t

▷ Calculate update coefficient β_t

▷ Update the mean vector and covariance matrix

Figure 11: SCW steps

2.1.3.7 Gradient Learning Classifier Algorithm

a) Constraint covered

The constraint of $y_t - \hat{y}_t = 0$ intuitive explanation is as follows $\max \left(\frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \right)$.

b) Brief presentation of the approach

Formally optimisation problem is as follows (the notation of our work is closer to lambda calculus and algorithmic game theoretic learning as opposed to convex optimisation, information-theoretic or statistically inspired approaches). The minimisation problem:

$$\min_{\theta} \sum (\theta_t - \theta_{t-1})^2$$

has constraint $\omega_t - \theta'_t x_t = 0$ where ω is the output and input are denoted by x_t with appropriate dimensions. The minimisation has closed form solution:

$$\theta_t = \theta_{t-1} + \frac{(\omega_t - \theta'_t x_t) x_t}{\|x_t\|^2}$$

The constraint can be considered as maximising accuracy. The accuracy constraint in the literature has been considered but not on the loss function as done in our work. For example, see (Kar et al., 2014) where the motivation is to *design consistent algorithms for a general learning problem objective and (optionally) constraints are defined by general functions of the confusion matrix.*

c) Steps of the algorithm

```

1: Initialize:  $\theta \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$ 
2: for each training example  $(x_i, y_i)$  do
3:                                      $\triangleright$  Predict label
4:    $\gamma_i \leftarrow \text{sign}(\langle \theta, x_i \rangle)$ 
5:                                      $\triangleright$  Calculate loss/error
6:    $\ell_i \leftarrow y_i - \gamma_i$ 
7:                                      $\triangleright$  Calculate learning rate  $\eta_i$ 
8:    $\eta_i \leftarrow \frac{\ell_i}{\|x_i\|_2 + \epsilon}$ 
9:                                      $\triangleright$  Update weight vector
10:   $\theta \leftarrow \theta + \eta_i y_i x_i$ 
11: end for

```

Figure 12: GLC

2.1.4 Validation of the offline constrained learning algorithms

2.1.4.1 Data description

The RBD24 dataset(s) comprise (s) various risk activities collected from real entities and users over a period of 15 days, with the samples segmented by Desktop (DE) and Smartphone (SM) devices. In the table below the imbalance ratio corresponds to the percentage of benign attacks (majority class) in the data.

To collect the dataset, multiple agents were deployed within an infrastructure of more than 3,000 entities, comprising laptops, workstations, and smartphone devices. The methods to build the ground truth are as follows:

- Simulator: Launched different realistic phishing campaigns, aiming to expose user credentials or disrupt access to a service.
- IDS (Intrusion Detection System): Deployed an IDS to collect various alerts associated with behavioural anomalies, such as crypto-mining or peer-to-peer traffic.

For each user exposed to the behaviours stated in the summary table, different Time Windows (TW) were computed by aggregating user behaviour within a fixed time interval. This TW serves as the basis for generating data for all supervised and unsupervised methods. See details in (Calvo et al., 2025).

The train-test split is performed on a user-by-user basis, ensuring that all records from any given user are contained entirely within either the training or the test set, but never both. This methodology is crucial for answering our primary research question: Can a model, trained on one cohort of users, accurately classify the behaviour of a completely new, previously unseen user?

Dataset	Train Size	Test Size	Imbalance Train (Majority/Total)	Imbalance Test (Majority/Total)
P2P desktop	164005	40319	79.40%	76.50%
Non Enc desktop	176599	44546	71.30%	78.90%
Phishing desktop	12919	4017	79.30%	89.96%
P2P smartphone	167755	40201	87.40%	85.19%
Non Enc smartphone	175671	46024	80.76%	83.38%
Phishing smartphone	35073	7901	77.83%	84.90%

Table 3: Data overview

2.1.4.2 Simulation results

In this section we report on the performance of the algorithms using the relevant metrics of false positive rate (FPR) and false negative rate (FNR) using the cybersecurity datasets from UC2. The parameter setting for all algorithms is shown in for all datasets. An 80/20 split was done, and algorithms were trained on a batch of the data. The trained parameters were used to forecast benign or malignant attacks on testing data.

Algorithm	Hyper-parameters
SbC	Threshold =10%
BAROW	$r = 0.1$
BAda-RDA	$\lambda = 0.01, \eta = 0.01, \delta = 0.1$
BRDA	$\lambda = 0.01, \gamma = 1$
BSCW	$C = 1, \eta = 0.5$

Table 4: Parameter setting

a) SbC Results

The SbC algorithms and its variants were executed on the datasets: **(1)** NN-Fbeta (no-balancing), **(2)** NN-BCE (no-balancing), **(3)** oversampling + NN-Fbeta (balancing), **(4)** oversampling + NN-BCE (balancing), **(5)** Undersampling + NN-Fbeta (balancing), **(6)** Undersampling + NN-BCE (balancing). Several sampling algorithms as indicated earlier were tested (see Figure 13)

Figure 13: Sampling techniques covered by the study

The two tables below show the results obtained on UC2 considering the best sampler at any step.

Datasets	Phishing Desktop	Phishing Smartphone	Non Enc Desktop	Non Enc Smartphone	P2P Desktop	P2P Smartphone
Algorithms						
SbC-No Balancing	72%	79%	38%	12%	14%	4%
BCE-No Balancing	83%	77%	69%	76%	68%	78%
SbC-Oversampling	58%	60%	7%	7%	50%	7%
BCE-Oversampling	84%	77%	70%	77%	68%	78%
SbC-Undersampling	74%	57%	8%	8%	15%	4%
BCE-Undersampling	84%	77%	69%	77%	68%	78%

Dataset	Phishing Desktop		Phishing Smartphone		Non Enc Desktop		Non Enc Smartphone		P2P Desktop		P2P Smartphone	
	FPR	FNR	FPR	FNR	FPR	FNR	FPR	FNR	FPR	FNR	FPR	FNR
SbC-No Balancing	31%	63%	12%	69%	76%	13%	95%	5%	97%	1%	100%	0%
BCE-No Balancing	11%	79%	14%	71%	19%	74%	4%	92%	7%	89%	3%	96%
SbC-Oversampling	53%	35%	49%	34%	100%	0%	98%	2%	64%	11%	99%	0%
BCE-Oversampling	9%	79%	15%	71%	15%	78%	4%	92%	6%	88%	2%	95%
SbC-Undersampling	30%	55%	49%	50%	100%	0%	98%	1%	96%	2%	100%	0%
BCE-Undersampling	8%	79%	16%	65%	17%	78%	4%	91%	6%	89%	3%	96%

Table 5: SbC results (F, FPR and FNR)

Some conclusions on each variant are discussed in the following:

1. Imbalanced

BCE: Low FPR, but FNR very high → misses most positives.

Surrogate: Lower FNR (better recall), but very high FPR → many false alarms.

2. Oversampled

BCE: Still high FNR, little improvement.

Surrogate: Strong recall, but FPR often extreme (up to 100%).

3. Undersampled

BCE: Same issue → high FNR, weak detection.

Surrogate: Balanced recall, but FPR very high in several cases.

Category	BCE behaviour	Surrogate behaviour
FPR extremes	Mostly low–moderate (3–19%)	Frequently very high (64–100%)
FNR extremes	Almost always extreme (65–96%)	Often controlled (0–35%, some 50–55%)
Minority class	Very poor, almost always misses phishing/P2P	Much better recall, but at high FPR
Phishing datasets	FNR consistently too high → unusable	Balanced FPR/FNR (though still high FPR in some cases)
Generalization	Overfits to majority class, fragile	More robust detection, but prone to over-flagging

Table 6: SbC results comparison

b) Results of Online to Batch Classification Algorithms

All the algorithms were executed on UC2 data using the parameters defined earlier.

Algorithm Initials	Phishing Desktop	Phishing Smartphone	Non Enc Desktop	Non Enc Smartphone	P2P Desktop	P2P Smartphone
BAda-RDA	18%	0%	34%	28%	0%	0%
BAROW	8%	1%	0%	28%	0%	26%
BGLC	20%	25%	2%	27%	2%	13%
BPA	30%	28%	4%	17%	11%	24%
BPerceptron	21%	24%	40%	28%	11%	25%
BRDA	12%	26%	2%	28%	4%	25%
BSCW	18%	6%	34%	26%	38%	8%

Dataset	Phishing desktop		Phishing smartphone		NonEnc desktop		NonEnc smartphone		P2P desktop		P2P smartphone	
Algorithm	FPR	FNR	FPR	FNR	FPR	FNR	FPR	FNR	FPR	FNR	FPR	FNR
BAda-RDA	100%	0%	0%	100%	100%	0%	100%	0%	0%	100%	0%	100%
BAROW	4%	94%	0%	99%	0%	100%	99%	1%	0%	100%	98%	1%
BGLC	76%	13%	100%	5%	1%	98%	97%	5%	2%	99%	11%	88%
BPA	14%	59%	48%	38%	3%	97%	52%	66%	7%	92%	75%	26%
BPerceptron	52%	31%	100%	6%	53%	23%	97%	4%	7%	93%	82%	15%
BRDA	26%	78%	99%	1%	2%	99%	100%	0%	5%	98%	99%	0%
BSCW	100%	0%	0%	96%	100%	0%	80%	22%	99%	1%	9%	93%

Table 7: Batch algorithm evaluation (I, FPR and FNR)

The results show that online to batch algorithms (denoted by the letter ‘B’) outperform the baseline (python library RCL implementation of binary cross entropy loss) on all datasets. The training is done on different users over time, but in the above setting after training no updates are made, which makes these algorithms perform poorly. The learned weights are fixed, and the temporal aspect is ignored.

The data features include user id and timestamp. The split is done such that the users in training set and test set don’t overlap, they are selected randomly by setting Hardy-Ramanujan number of 1729

as random seed for reproducibility. Each user data includes temporal structure, which is something we ignore in this setting -- explaining the poor F-score in the above table. It is well known that data indexed by time almost always violates the assumption of being independent identically distributed.

To further explore the performance of these algorithms, we proposed an additional variant. It consists of combining offline and online learning, hence the prefix H for the algorithms (standing for hybrid). The algorithms start with offline learning similarly to the previous experiment. Then an online pass is run on the test sample (which represents blocks of data associated with unseen users). The scores are computed as per the standard way, meaning on individual rows of the data (and not per user).

Table 8 shows the results obtained by each algorithm on each dataset.

Algorithm Initials	Phishing Desktop	Phishing Smartphone	Non Enc Desktop	Non Enc Smartphone	P2P Desktop	P2P Smartphone
HPA	98%	98%	99%	99%	99%	99%
HPerceptron	96%	97%	98%	98%	98%	98%
HGLC	96%	97%	99%	98%	99%	98%
HAROW	99%	99%	99%	99%	99%	99%
HRDA	98%	98%	99%	99%	99%	99%
HSCW	1%	7%	98%	97%	99%	23%
HAda-RDA	97%	99%	99%	99%	99%	99%

Table 8: Hybrid algorithms evaluation using $F_{\beta=1}$

It is easy to see from the quality of the results obtained, the positive effect of keeping the memory of the algorithm “fresh” to capture the patterns of malicious attacks on user’s smartphone or desktop after a sequence of interactions. Indeed, apart from SCW, all other algorithms do well on all datasets. The computational demands of this variant are quite high which may require distributed training. This becomes more vital when considering how data is generated. Many data points are generated at the same timestamp for each user, making the ingestion of data a challenge on its own. Parallel update could be a way forward to address this problem.

2.1.5 Conclusions about offline simulation results

By comparing F1-score we get a comprehensive overview of the simulations. The ability to be applicable to both batch and online is advantageous. All hybrid algorithms obtain very high F1-score as shown in Figure 14. The surrogate loss-based classification underperforms the baseline BCE, while the baseline does not improve by much for under and over sampling techniques, indicating that sampling in this case might just be a computational overhead. Figure 14 shows that only hybrid approach outperforms the baseline, HAROW being most consistent. Only HSCW underperforms the baseline on Phishing datasets and P2P smartphone.

Figure 14: Comparison of algorithms

2.2 Continual and online learning

In this subsection we discuss two cases of learning, in the first case we will consider a non-stationary data stream to study forgetting of algorithms. The objective of the first case is to understand the forgetting and performance. In second learning scenario our focus will be on predictive performance.

As an alternative approach to (Crammer et al., 2006b, 2009; Duchi & Singer, 2009; J. Wang et al., 2016b; Xiao, 2010) where hinge loss is used, we propose novel learning algorithms that rely on Lagrange multipliers.

In terms of continual learning, we build on the proposed online learning algorithms to formulate binary classification problems as task-agnostic learning problem considering two scenarios:

- **Case 1:** treating each distinct dataset in UC2 as a new (sequential task).
- **Case 2:** treating each dataset as a sequential set of batches - moving window of fixed size (sequential task).

2.2.1 Continual Learning

A continual learning setup consists of a sequence of N tasks, denoted by the set $T = \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_N\}$. Each task T_i is associated with a specific data distribution D_i from which samples (x, y) are drawn, where x belongs to the input X_i and y belongs to label space Y_i .

In Task incremental learning, learning is from a sequence of distinct tasks. Typically, it is assumed that during inference a task identifier is provided alongside x , but we are not required any identifier in our formulation, for these reasons the proposed learning scheme is task-agnostic. *Task incremental learning* encompasses of scenarios where the label spaces of the tasks may be completely different. Any two distinct tasks T_i and T_j with $i \neq j$, which leads to $Y_i \cap Y_j = \emptyset$ for $i \neq j$. The label space of the entire learning problem is $Y_{total} = \cup_{i=1}^N Y_i$. All the sets are disjoint, so the total label space is the sum of individual label spaces $|Y_{total}| = \sum |Y_i|$. *Domain incremental* is a special case of *task incremental learning*. In domain incremental learning the label space is not disjoint i.e.; sequence of tasks shares the exact same label space. Thus, $\cup_{i=1}^N Y_i = Y$. On the other hand, *class incremental learning* is like *task incremental learning*, but with the distinction of having no task-id and each task corresponds to learning a new class. At test time the model is presented with a sample x from any of the tasks seen so far to predict from the union of label spaces without being presented with a task id. For further details consult (de Ven et al., 2022; Z. Wang et al., 2024).

In our case, the label space is binary, and we are providing no task ID making this *Task Agnostic Domain Incremental learning* or broadly speaking *Task Agnostic Continual Learning*. The set of possible outputs across all tasks is always binary. The objective is not to learn new classes, but to learn to recognise the same classes under different conditions or from different data distributions. We do not provide task ID's which makes the learning process *Task-Agnostic*. The challenge is to avoid forgetting of past distribution of same classes.

This experimental design, where different datasets are used to train and test the models over time, allowing us to systematically measure both predictive performance and the degree of forgetting. Our primary focus is to quantify and compare forgetting by various algorithms. More precisely, we will consider the following setup:

- Tasks: A sequence of N tasks $T = \{T_1, \dots, T_N\}$.
- Data: Each task T_j has data distribution D_j where samples are (x_i, y_i) and $y_i \in \{-1, 1\}$.
- Model: An algorithm A_k with parameters θ_j , after training on task T_1, \dots, T_j .
- Training Protocol: The parameters are updated sequentially: $\theta_j = \text{Train}(A_k(\theta_{j-1}), D_j)$, where Train represents the training process for task j .
- Accuracy Matrix: The performance matrix R_k for algorithm A_k is defined as $R_k[i, j] = \text{Accuracy}(A_k(\theta_j), D_i)$ for $i \leq j$.
- Forgetting Metric: The forgetting F_k caused by learning task T_j is the average performance drop on all previously seen tasks:
-

$$F_k(j) = \frac{1}{j-1} \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} \max(0, R_k[i, j-1] - R_k[i, j])$$

We now formulate moving window of fix size as continual learning's task agnostic domain incremental learning. In this setup we will consider our batches as task. More precisely,

- Tasks: The process consists of a sequence of N' tasks, $T = \{T_w, T_{w+1}, \dots, T_{N-1}\}$ where N is the total number of samples and W is the window size. Each task T_j corresponds to training and prediction step at time j .
- Data: Each task T_j uses a specific subset of the overall dataset $D = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=0}^{N-1}$. The data for T_j is the training window $D_j^{\text{train}} = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=j-W}^{j-1}$ and a single test sample $D_j^{\text{test}} = (x_j, y_j)$, where $x_i \in R^d$ and $y_i \in \{-1, 1\}$.
- Call: An algorithm A_k is defined by a set of parameters (weights) $\theta \in R^d$. Let θ_j be the parameters of algorithm A_k after it has been trained on the data for task T_j .
- Training: The model parameters are updated sequentially. The state of the model before task T_j is θ_{j-1} . This state is updated to θ_j by training on the window D_j^{train} . The Train represents the update: $\theta_j = \text{Train}(A_k(\theta_{j-1}), D_j^{\text{train}})$
- Forgetting: The performance matrix R_k for algorithm A_k would be defined as the accuracy of the model trained up to task j on the test data from a previous task i :

$$R_k[i, j] = \text{Accuracy}(A_k(\theta_j), D_i^{\text{test}}) \text{ for } i \leq j$$

The single step ahead accuracy, which corresponds to the diagonal elements $R_k[i, j]$. The forgetting F_k caused by learning tasks would be the average performance drop on all previously seen tasks computing the degradation of past tasks after learning the new one.

$$F_k(j) = \frac{1}{j-1} \sum_{i=W}^{j-1} \max(0, R_k[i, j-1] - R_k[i, j])$$

Require:

$\mathcal{A} = \{A_1, \dots, A_K\}$: A set of online learning algorithm classes.
 $\mathcal{T} = \{\mathcal{T}_1, \dots, \mathcal{T}_N\}$: A sequence of N tasks.
For each task \mathcal{T}_j , a training set D_j^{train} and a test set D_j^{test} .

Initialization:

```

1: for each algorithm class  $A_k \in \mathcal{A}$  do
2:    $M_k \leftarrow A_k.\text{initialize}()$  ▷ Initialize a model for each algorithm
3:    $R_k \leftarrow \text{create\_matrix}(N, N, \text{fill}=\text{NaN})$  ▷ Performance matrix for algorithm  $A_k$ 
4: end for
5:  $S \leftarrow \{\}$  ▷ Initialize empty map to store a scaler for each task

```

Main Continual Learning Loop:

```

6: for  $j = 1$  to  $N$  do ▷  $j$  is the index of the current task being trained
7:    $(X_{\text{train}}, y_{\text{train}}) \leftarrow D_j^{\text{train}}$ 
   // 1. Pre-process and Train on the current task
8:    $\text{scaler}_j \leftarrow \text{StandardScaler}().\text{fit}(X_{\text{train}})$ 
9:    $S[j] \leftarrow \text{scaler}_j$  ▷ Store scaler for this task
10:   $X_{\text{train\_scaled}} \leftarrow S[j].\text{transform}(X_{\text{train}})$ 
11:  for each model  $M_k \in \{M_1, \dots, M_K\}$  do
12:    for each sample  $(x_i, y_i) \in (X_{\text{train\_scaled}}, y_{\text{train}})$  do
13:       $M_k.\text{partial\_fit}(x_i, y_i)$  ▷ Update model parameters
14:    end for
15:  end for
   // 2. Evaluation Phase
   After training on  $\mathcal{T}_j$ , evaluate on all tasks seen so far ( $\mathcal{T}_1$  to  $\mathcal{T}_j$ ).
16:  for  $i = 1$  to  $j$  do ▷  $i$  is the index of the task being evaluated on
17:     $(X_{\text{test}}, y_{\text{test}}) \leftarrow D_i^{\text{test}}$ 
18:     $X_{\text{test\_scaled}} \leftarrow S[i].\text{transform}(X_{\text{test}})$  ▷ Use the original scaler for task  $i$ 
19:    for each model  $M_k \in \{M_1, \dots, M_K\}$  do
20:       $\text{accuracy} \leftarrow M_k.\text{evaluate}(X_{\text{test\_scaled}}, y_{\text{test}})$ 
21:       $R_k[i, j] \leftarrow \text{accuracy}$  ▷ Store accuracy in the performance matrix
22:    end for
23:  end for
24: end for

```

Figure 15: Continual Learning case 1

Require:

$\mathcal{A} = \{A_1, \dots, A_K\}$: A set of learning algorithm classes.
 $\mathcal{T} = \{\mathcal{T}_1, \dots, \mathcal{T}_N\}$: A sequence of N tasks.
For each task \mathcal{T}_j , a training set D_j^{train} and a test set D_j^{test} .

Initialization:

```

1: for each algorithm class  $A_k \in \mathcal{A}$  do
2:    $M_k \leftarrow A_k.\text{initialize}()$  ▷ Initialize a model for each algorithm
3:    $R_k \leftarrow \text{create\_matrix}(N, N, \text{fill}=\text{NaN})$  ▷ Performance matrix for algorithm  $A_k$ 
4: end for
5:  $S \leftarrow \{\}$  ▷ Initialize empty map to store a scaler for each task

```

Main Continual Learning Loop:

```

6: for  $j = 1$  to  $N$  do ▷  $j$  is the index of the current task being trained
7:    $(X_{\text{train}}, y_{\text{train}}) \leftarrow D_j^{\text{train}}$ 
   // 1. Pre-process and Train on the current task
8:    $\text{scaler}_j \leftarrow \text{StandardScaler}().\text{fit}(X_{\text{train}})$ 
9:    $S[j] \leftarrow \text{scaler}_j$  ▷ Store scaler for this task
10:   $X_{\text{train\_scaled}} \leftarrow S[j].\text{transform}(X_{\text{train}})$ 
11:  for each model  $M_k \in \{M_1, \dots, M_K\}$  do
12:    for each sample  $(x_i, y_i) \in (X_{\text{train\_scaled}}, y_{\text{train}})$  do
13:       $M_k.\text{partial\_fit}(x_i, y_i)$  ▷ Update model parameters
14:    end for
15:  end for
   // 2. Evaluation Phase
   After training on  $\mathcal{T}_j$ , evaluate on all tasks seen so far ( $\mathcal{T}_1$  to  $\mathcal{T}_j$ ).
16:  for  $i = 1$  to  $j$  do ▷  $i$  is the index of the task being evaluated on
17:     $(X_{\text{test}}, y_{\text{test}}) \leftarrow D_i^{\text{test}}$ 
18:     $X_{\text{test\_scaled}} \leftarrow S[i].\text{transform}(X_{\text{test}})$  ▷ Use the original scaler for task  $i$ 
19:    for each model  $M_k \in \{M_1, \dots, M_K\}$  do
20:       $\text{accuracy} \leftarrow M_k.\text{evaluate}(X_{\text{test\_scaled}}, y_{\text{test}})$ 
21:       $R_k[i, j] \leftarrow \text{accuracy}$  ▷ Store accuracy in the performance matrix
22:    end for
23:  end for
24: end for

```

Figure 16: Continual learning case 2

In both learning protocols we will be processing batches. The protocols of continual learning consider arrival of features and label simultaneously as a training batch.

2.2.2 Online Learning

In this scenario the learning is done example by example sequentially. The protocol processes feature and makes forecast only after making the forecast the true label is used or revealed. At each time step the learning algorithm receive information, which it processes to forecast the label. Once prediction is made the true label is received to adjust. The process continues iteratively.

Require: A set of possible actions \mathcal{K}

Require: A time horizon $T > 0$

- 1: **Initialize:** Learner's internal state.
- 2: **for** $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ **do**
- 3: The Learner selects a point (or action) $x_t \in \mathcal{K}$ based on past information.
- 4: The Environment simultaneously selects a loss function $f_t : \mathcal{K} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.
- 5: The loss function f_t is revealed to the Learner.
- 6: The Learner incurs the loss $f_t(x_t)$.
- 7: The Learner uses the information from f_t (e.g., its value or its gradient $\nabla f_t(x_t)$) to update its internal state for the next round.

Figure 17: Online learning protocol

2.2.3 Validation on streaming scenario

2.2.3.1 Data description

To simulate a continuous data stream, we use the same data described in Sec. 2.3.1. The data is first chronologically ordered. Events sharing the same timestamp are then aggregated by summing their features, creating a unified time-series. The central objective of this study is to determine whether we can accurately classify network traffic as malicious or benign as this data stream evolves over time.

Dataset ID	Observed Behaviour	Size	Imbalance Ratio (Majority class/Total)
Crypto desktop	Miner Checking	3794	72%
Crypto smartphone	Miner Checking	2945	69%
Out Flash desktop	Outdated software components	3794	34%
Out Flash smartphone	Outdated software components	2964	88%
Out TLS desktop	Outdated TLS protocol	3794	61%
Out TLS smartphone	Outdated TLS protocol	2987	73%
P2P desktop	P2P Activity	3797	75%
P2P smartphone	P2P Activity	3021	61%
Non Enc desktop	Non-encrypted password	3811	54%
Non Enc smartphone	Non-encrypted password	2945	64%
Phishing desktop	Phishing email	1209	65%
Phishing smartphone	Phishing email	1313	90%

Table 9: Data overview

2.2.3.2 Experiment settings

Experiment 1: Task in this experiment is a dataset; thus, all datasets are considered at once. 500 data points of a task then tested on size of 10 of other tasks. The assumption in this setup is that learning from one task is sufficient to forecast next 10 points. This assumption is likely to hold when tasks have same data generating mechanism over time. In other words, in any point in time the distribution of one task and any other task is the same.

Experiment 2: Task in this experiment is the batch within the dataset. A fixed size of 250 is used to store in the memory and forecast the next step. The assumption here is that the forecasted data and the training data are from the same distribution. To make this assumption plausible, we will only forecast one step ahead.

Experiment 3: Considering an incoming stream of data and we make no assumptions on the underlying nature of the data.

Experiment 1 and Experiment 2 frameworks are easier to integrate to scale in most if not all platforms. The algorithms developed in task 3.4 (and many others from literature) can be written as classes and then those classes can be called. Experiment 3 does not require a framework to scale per say, as only vectors are being processed, thus is extremely efficient.

2.2.3.3 Simulation results

Experiment 1: The main objective of continual learning is stated as the goal of continual learning is to learn non-stationarity without forgetting the previous knowledge (L. Wang et al., 2024). The source of forgetting is data distribution shift. Figure 18 is to validate the previous statement. The grey dotted vertical line in the plot illustrates the concept drift points, this vertical line is drawn on the chart at the beginning of a training, where the type of task changes for the first time. It acts as a visual separator to show the drift. The performance metrics show none achieves reliable performance in this continual learning setup. The result highlights the typical problem in continual learning. Over the period forgetting on tasks get lower, but the performance is affected.

Figure 18: Visualizing catastrophic forgetting

Experiment 2: The analysis of the results shown in Table 10: Continual learning simulation results reveals that the Passive-Aggressive (PA) algorithm is the dominant algorithm, achieving the best error balance on most datasets.

Dataset	Algorithm	FNR	FPR	Forgetting	Deviation
Crypto desktop	PA	16%	6%	0.70%	4.00%
Crypto smartphone	PA	25%	8%	1.10%	5.80%

Non Enc desktop	PA	11%	5%	0.70%	2.70%
Non Enc smartphone	PA	15%	12%	1.60%	4.80%
Out Flash desktop	GL Perceptron	9%	3%	0.60%	1.60%
Out Flash smartphone	Ada-RDA	7%	9%	3.40%	9.70%
Out TLS desktop	PA	13%	4%	0.50%	3.80%
Out TLS smartphone	Ada-RDA	9%	16%	5.30%	12.50%
P2P desktop	Ada-RDA	5%	9%	3.10%	10.20%
P2P smartphone	GL / Perceptron	20%	13%	2.70%	5.40%
Phishing desktop	Ada-RDA	7%	14%	6.70%	9.90%
Phishing smartphone	PA	13%	24%	1.70%	5.00%

Table 10: Continual learning simulation results

Experiment 3: Table 11: Online learning simulation results shows that the GLC algorithm is the definitive top performer across every single dataset in this online setting. Unlike scenarios where different algorithms excel on different data types, GLC consistently achieves the best balance between FNR and FPR.

Dataset	Algorithm	FNR	FPR
Crypto desktop	OGLC	13%	4%
Crypto smartphone	OGLC	16%	5%
Non Enc desktop	OGLC	6%	14%
Non Enc smartphone	OGLC	7%	20%
Out Flash desktop	OGLC	5%	4%
Out Flash smartphone	OGLC	6%	7%
Out TLS desktop	OGLC	7%	3%
Out TLS smartphone	OGLC	13%	9%
P2P desktop	OGLC	5%	4%
P2P smartphone	OGLC	11%	17%
Phishing desktop	OGLC	5%	15%
Phishing smartphone	OGLC	4%	40%

Table 11: Online learning simulation results

2.2.3.4 Discussion of the online learning results

Figure 19 shows that on Out TLS desktop, Crypto desktop, Non Enc smartphone and phishing desktop OGLC is better than the best alternative by over 10% on both FP and FN indicated by the green arrows. The orange arrows indicate that OGLC improves FPR by over 10% while giving reasonable FNR. For Out Flash desktop PA provides 0% FNR but FPR is 100%, the closest to OGLC is ADA-RDA with 5% FNR and 7% FPR, the improvement is on FPR while FNR is the same.

Figure 19: Proposed Online vs Online State-of-the-art

The improvement is below 10% on FPR, such cases are represented by orange arrow at line passing through $y = 0$. The orange arrow below the line $y = 0$ are the case where the best alternative improves by small percentage but there is high increase in FPR. For example, the most extreme case is the orange arrow of Phishing smartphone, where ADA-RDA improves FNR by 1% but FPR is worse by over 10%. To develop further understanding, two existing explainable AI tools SHAP and LIME (Salih et al., 2025) are used.

OGLC algorithm obtains the most “balanced” or least amount of trade-off in result. It is the only algorithm that outperforms all algorithms on both measures on four datasets.

Figure 20: LIME benign and malicious threats

Figure 20 shows that *non-working hours http* is 35.83 which is significant amount of HTTP traffic occurred outside of normal business hours. This is a strong indicator of a threat. A high ratio of DNS queries came from non-standard source ports, which is unusual for normal clients. SSL resumed ratio

of 64.47 is threatening. An analyst looking at this can see that the combination of off-hours HTTP traffic, DNS errors, and unusual port usage were the primary reason for the alert. In Figure 20:

- Features highlighted in orange are evidence pushing the prediction towards "Malicious Threat". Features highlighted in blue are evidence pushing the prediction towards "Benign Threat".
- The length of each bar represents the strength or weight of that feature's contribution. Longer bars have a bigger impact.
- The number next to each bar is the numerical weight assigned by local LIME model.

In Figure 21, The text next to the bars tells you the specific condition of the feature that led to this conclusion. It shows that a burst of rapid DNS queries, a high rate of DNS errors, or significant HTTP/DNS traffic outside of normal working hours are the strongest indicators of a threat. Conversely, traffic from known high-ID entities or traffic that conforms to standard protocols (like normal SMTP) can generally be considered safe.

Figure 21: SHAP impact plot

In Figure 22, OGCL's most striking feature is the dark blue line, identified in the legend as http response body length ratio. The model rapidly assigns it a strong negative importance to it. A high ratio of HTTP body length to header length is a good indicator of benign traffic.

Figure 22: OGCL top five features across all datasets

2.3 Physics-Informed learning

Climate change associated with an excessive urbanization increases the frequency of hazard events. Cities are facing more often these phenomena. In our study, we are considering a certain kind of flood called “flash flood.” They are caused by heavy rainfalls. The event is in general fast and last few days. Currently, physical methods are used to modelized these hazards. In an operational context, these kinds of models are unusable due to their slow time of inference. The deployment of methods is necessary to help the actors to take fast decisions.

The characteristics helped us to make assumptions facilitate the study. The duration the flood event makes us consider the ground in an urban area as impermeable layer, as a short interval of time does not allow the soil to absorb. We can expect the water to flow in the direction of the slope. On another hand, areas with an important stress of urbanization have a high density of buildings. The developed model will then need to deal with data at high-resolution to give an accurate account of the situation in the narrow streets.

Time prediction is also to be defined. This variable depends mostly on two things: the data availability and the operational needs. We are considering in the study a catchment located in the region of Nimes. In this area, actors have estimated that a 30-minute prediction will be necessary to correctly catch the events. To forecast flood, the usable data set is large, and their nature are various. In that way, implemented a flood prediction model is also dealing with multimodal data.

First, there is the topographical information, from this data we are retrieving knowledges of the studied area. In this project we are using the following information:

- The Digital Elevation Model (DEM): a tile where each pixel is representing the elevation of the ground. In the use case, the product use is IGN RGE ALTI, available at two resolutions 5 and 1 meters. DEM layer will be represented as a 2D map.
- The building footprints: in the study we are dealing with urban areas. Buildings are playing a major role in the water flow behaviour during an event. It exists two ways to get this product, with OSM (Open Street Map) building layer or with classified point clouds from IGN LiDAR HD. Building mask will be represented as a 2D map.

Then, meteorological information is gathered to characterize the event, we are using:

- Rainfall information from the Calamar (CALcul de LAMes d’eau radAR) product. This spatial-temporal data gives us an insight of the situation every 5 minutes for the duration of the event. The temporal aspect of the data adds a new dimension to input model. The number of data

needed depends on the time prediction. For 30 minutes prediction, six-time steps data are necessary. Rainfall data resolution is quite low, 300 meters. During the data preprocessing phase, it will be aligned to the rest of the data.

Finally, the water depth is also given as an input to report the initial flood situation as the beginning of the event. The data is represented as a 2D map where each pixel the level of the water at the initial time.

For each sample of input is associated a ground truth, the 2D map represents on each pixel the water level. The top left plot shows Digital Elevation Model (DEM), the top right shows average rainfall over half hour, the bottom left is the water depth at the beginning of the prediction and the output of the predicted water level 30 min later. Figure 23 shows (from top left to bottom right) the elevation, rainfall water depth before and after.

Figure 23: Flash flood dataset characteristics

2.3.1 Physics-informed learning architecture

The proposed model is a sequence-to-sequence architecture designed to process the history of 2D spatial maps and predict a future state. It is composed of a Conv LSTM-based Encoder and Decoder. The selection of the autoregressive Encoder-Decoder Conv LSTM architecture is used due to the inherent complexities of flash flood data and the demands of the forecasting task. Flash flood data is fundamentally spatiotemporal. It consists of a sequence of 2D spatial maps where the value at each grid cell (e.g., water depth) is highly correlated with its neighbours (spatial dependency) and its own past values (temporal dependency). A model must be able to understand both types of correlation simultaneously.

- The standard Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) or Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network would require flattening each 2D map into a 1D vector, thereby destroying the critical spatial topology.
- A standard Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is good at extracting spatial features from a single image but lacks the internal memory (recurrent connections) to model temporal evolution.

By replacing the internal matrix multiplications of a standard LSTM with convolution operations, the Conv LSTM cell can preserve the 2D spatial structure of the input (Shi et al., 2015). Its internal states are 3D tensors, allowing it to learn and propagate localized spatiotemporal patterns, such as the shape, direction, and velocity of a flood wave, through time. The Encoder-Decoder architecture provides a robust paradigm for sequence-to-sequence tasks (Cho et al., 2014; Sutskever et al., 2014).

Figure 24: Physics-Informed Auto-regressive Encoder-Decoder Conv LSTM architecture (ARC-Conv LSTM)

2.3.2 Problem formulation

The Physics-informed Neural Networks (PINNs) optimization² problem is formulated as follows:

$$\min L_{total} = \min(L_{data} + aL_{physics})$$

where L_{data} is the data fidelity term, $L_{physics}$ is the physics-based regularisation term and a is the hyperparameter. The masked Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the predicted water depth \hat{h} and the true water depth h :

$$L_{data}(\theta) = \frac{1}{|\Omega|} \sum_{i \in \Omega} (\hat{h}(x_i, t + 1; \theta) - h(x_i, t + 1))^2$$

Where Ω is the set of valid spatial pixels. The physics term measures the extent to which model's prediction violates the 2D Shallow Water Equations (SWEs). The loss is the mean squared residual of

² The optimizer used is from (Kingma & Ba, 2014).

the conservation of mass and momentum equations. The above problem is addressed via following protocol (Figure 25):

```

1: for each epoch do
2:   Set model to training mode: model.train()
3:   for each batch (X, Y, D, R, M) in train_loader do
4:      $\hat{Y} \leftarrow \text{model}(X, D, R)$                                 ▷ Forward pass
5:     loss  $\leftarrow \text{masked\_mse\_loss}(\hat{Y}_h, Y, M)$                 ▷ Loss on water depth
6:     optimizer.zero_grad()
7:     loss.backward()                                                ▷ Backpropagation
8:     optimizer.step()                                              ▷ Update weights
9:   Set model to evaluation mode: model.eval()
10:  with torch.no_grad() do
11:    for each batch (X, Y, D, R, M) in val_loader do
12:       $\hat{Y} \leftarrow \text{model}(X, D, R)$ 
13:      val_loss  $\leftarrow \text{masked\_mse\_loss}(\hat{Y}_h, Y, M)$ 
14:    end with
15:    Record average training and validation loss for the epoch.

```

Figure 25: Autoregressive encoder-decoder Cov LSTM training and validation protocol

After training, the model's performance is assessed by generating a multi-step forecast autoregressively. The model is initialized with a sequence, predicts step $t + 1$, and this prediction is then used as input to predict step $t + 2$. This process is repeated to generate a full forecast sequence.

2.3.3 Initial study

Figure 26 shows a very healthy and successful training process. All four lines are consistently decreasing over the 50 epochs. This is the primary and most important sign of successful learning. It is not just getting better at fitting the data (Data Loss is decreasing), but it is also getting better at obeying the laws of physics (Physics Loss is decreasing). The validation line closely tracks the training line, which is learning the underlying physical patterns in a way that generalizes unseen data. Overfitting occurs when the training data fit is too well. This would be visually represented by the training loss continuing to decrease while the validation loss starts to increase. Since the validation loss is consistently decreasing alongside the training loss, there is no evidence of overfitting in this 50-epoch run. The fact that both losses are decreasing together suggests a synergistic relationship. By epoch 50, all lines are beginning to flatten out, especially the physics loss curves.

Figure 26: Physics informed learning visual

2.4 Unified embedding and clustering

2.4.1 Description of UEC

a) Constraint covered

In contrast to methods (Chang et al., 2017; Ghasedi Dizaji et al., 2017; Guo et al., 2020; Hu et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2014; Ji et al., 2017; Xie et al., 2016; Yan et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2016) that perform embedding followed by clustering or alternating between embedding and clustering to cluster highly dimensional data, the present work (Allaoui et al., 2024) proposes a bi-objective loss function that combines data embedding and clustering that preserves the data's original structure in the embedding space aiming at producing a better clustering assignment of data points. In other terms such approach imposes a constraint on the topology of the data during clustering or equivalently imposing a constraint on grouping of data while embedding it in a lower dimensionality space. The combined loss is optimised using three different ways: (1) Comma Variant, (2) Plus Variant, and (3) Light Plus Variant.

b) Brief presentation of the approach

UEC is about mapping high D -dimensional input data onto a d -dimensional embedded space while considering clustering constraints, where $d \ll D$. To achieve that, UEC optimises the following objective function:

$$F = \alpha CE \oplus \beta KL$$

where CE is the cross-entropy loss that assesses the quality of the embedding in the low-dimensional space (referred to as the embedding loss). KL is the Kullback-Leibler divergence and is used to assess the clustering quality (referred to as the clustering loss). The quantities α and β define the relative weights of the two loss components. The elaborated version of the above equation is:

$$F(P, Q, T, S) = \alpha CE(P, Q) \oplus \beta KL(T||S)$$

CE computes the total entropy between the affinity matrix P (that represents the similarity scores between pairs of data points) and the affinity matrix Q (that represents the similarity scores between each embedded data point and its neighbours).

$CE(P, Q)$ is expressed as follows:

$$CE(P, Q) = \sum_i \sum_j \left(p_{ij} \log \left(\frac{p_{ij}}{q_{ij}} \right) + (1 - p_{ij}) \log \left(\frac{1 - p_{ij}}{1 - q_{ij}} \right) \right)$$

On the other hand KL measures the relative entropy (divergence) between the soft assignments S (which stand for a smooth approximation of the membership strength between the embedded points z_i and the cluster centres in the embedded space μ_k) and the auxiliary target distribution T (obtained by normalising the membership of data points by the sum of the memberships of other data points in the same cluster).

The formulation of $KL(T||S)$ is as follows:

$$KL(T||S) = \sum_i \sum_k \left(T_{ik} \log \left(\frac{T_{ik}}{S_{ik}} \right) \right)$$

More details on the formulation of P, Q, T , and S can be found in (Allaoui et al. 2024). We can optimise the $F(P, Q, T, S)$ loss function (composing an embedding optimisation problem and a clustering optimisation problem) in three ways. Each way corresponds to an interpretation of the \oplus symbol:

- i. $\oplus = ','$ (comma) UEC takes one gradient step for the embedding optimisation problem, passes the new parameters to the clustering optimisation problem, takes one gradient step for the second optimisation problem, then passes the estimated parameters to the

first optimisation problem again, and repeats this alternating sequence. This scenario is referred to as a *sequential update*.

- ii. $\oplus = '+'$ (plus) indicates that the evaluation of the total loss $F(P, Q, T, S)$ is done in one combined step (bi-objective function) to update the sought quantities simultaneously. This scenario is referred to as *joint update*.
- iii. $\oplus = \text{light '+'}$ (light plus) is a more efficient version of (ii) in terms of computational time and consist of freezing some quantities during the computation of the gradient step.

c) Steps of the algorithm

The UEC algorithm is given as follows:

Algorithm 1 UEC

Input: Dataset $Y = \{y_i\}_{i=1}^n$, number of cluster C , dimension of the embedding space d , min-dist, number of nearest neighbours nn

Output: Embedded dataset $Z = \{z_i\}_{i=1}^n$, set of centres $M = \{\mu_k\}_{k=1}^C$.

- 1: Construct the graph of the original data
 - 2: Compute the affinity matrix for the input data Y
 - 3: Initialise the embedding space of dimension d .
 - 4: Initialise the cluster centres.
 - 5: **while** The convergence criterion is not met **do**
 - 6: Compute the affinity matrix for the embedded data Z .
 - 7: Compute the soft assignment of the embedded data to the clusters $S(Z, M)$
 - 8: Compute the probabilistic point-to-cluster assignments using the obtained soft assignment $\mathcal{T}(Z, M)$.
 - 9: Update the coordinates of the embedded data Z .
 - 10: Update the centres
 - 11: **end while**
-

Figure 27: UEC Algorithm steps

2.4.2 Simulation results

The experimental simulations are run on several real-world datasets such as USPS (9298 images with 10 classes), MNIST (70,000 images with 10 classes), CIFAR10 (60000 images with 10 classes), and Reuters 10K (10700 documents with 4 classes) using two (2) evaluation measures which are: Accuracy (Acc) and Normalised Mutual Information (NMI). Table 12 shows the performance of the three variants of UEC on two datasets, while Table 13 portrays the performance (in terms of accuracy) of UEC on the 4 datasets against other baselines.

Table 12: Comparison of the three UEC variants

Models	Dataset			
	USPS		MNIST	
	ACC	NMI	ACC	NMI
Comma variant	0.967	0.928	0.959	0.932
Plus variant	0.982	0.948	0.988	0.956
Light plus variant	0.979	0.937	0.986	0.950

Table 13: UEC vs. other algorithms

Models	Dataset			
	USPS	MNIST	CIFAR-10	Reuters
k-means	0.668	0.572	0.228	0.524
DEC	0.619	0.843	0.301	0.722
JULE	0.950	0.964	0.271	-
IMSAT	0.976	0.984	0.456	0.719
DEPICT	0.964	0.965	0.342	-
DAC	0.972	0.978	0.522	-
Spectral Net	0.965	0.971	0.322	0.803
DERC	0.977	0.975	0.374	-
DynAE	0.981	0.987	0.530	-
GCML	0.958	0.980	0.431	0.836
UEC (Plus variant)	0.982	0.988	0.534	0.965
UEC (Light plus variant)	0.979	0.986	0.526	0.962

These results clearly show that UEC is competitive with the state-of-the-art embedding and clustering methods. In particular, UEC allows for better preservation of the structure of the dataset resulting in better clustering performance.

3 Model selection using meta-learning

3.1 Motivation

The selection of an appropriate machine learning algorithm/model for a given task remains a significant challenge, often relying on a practitioner's prior experience and an exhaustive, trial-and-error experimentation process. This ad-hoc approach can lead to inefficient workflows and suboptimal model performance. To introduce a more systematic methodology, this work explores the development of a meta-learning algorithm³ capable of recommending relevant algorithms based on historical performance (i.e., from previous experiments). The proposed algorithm leverages meta-learning principles by comparing a new dataset against a large repository to find statistically similar instances. Based on the known outcomes of algorithms on these similar datasets, the system can infer and recommend which models are most likely to succeed, thereby helping to accelerate the lengthy experimentation phase. The implementation of this concept involves the integration of dataset similarity metrics, a performance database, and a simple user interface.

3.2 Meta-learning algorithm for model selection

The overall steps of the algorithm are as follows:

- 1- Given a dataset D and the set of datasets from previous experiments $\{S_i\}_{i=1,n}$ stored along with algorithms/models (along with their performance) used during the experiments
- 2- Compute m meta-features for both D and each S_i , referred to as F and $\{G_i\}_{i=1,n}$
- 3- Compute the distance between F and each G_i using the summed distance through a P-Norm (L_p)

- a. $Dist(F, G_i) = \left(\sum_{j=1}^m |F_j - G_{ij}| \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$

- 4- Rank the distances and select the most similar data set as follows:

- a. $k = \underset{1 \leq i \leq n}{\operatorname{argmin}} Dist(F, G_i)$

³ We will refer to it as “tool” where appropriate to avoid using the word “algorithm” and thus alleviating ambiguity associated with this word in this context of meta-learning.

5- Select the $t (\geq 1)$ top performing models $\{A_l\}_{l=1,t}$ on the selected S_k

As indicated in Step 2, the model selection algorithm computes some meta-features of the input dataset and stored datasets. For these later, the meta-features can already be computed and stored as soon such datasets become available. In this work we rely on the meta-features listed in Table 14. In particular, we used simple meta-features, statistical meta-features, and PCA meta-features (Feurer, 2015).

Table 14: A list of meta-features considered

<p>Simple metafeatures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of patterns log number of patterns number of classes number of features log number of features number of patterns with missing values percentage of patterns with missing values number of features with missing values percentage of features with missing values number of missing values percentage of missing values number of numeric features number of categorical features ratio numerical to categorical ratio categorical to numerical dataset dimensionality log dataset dimensionality inverse dataset dimensionality log inverse dataset dimensionality class probability min class probability max class probability mean class probability std <p>Information-theoretic metafeature:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> class entropy 	<p>Statistical metafeatures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min # categorical values max # categorical values mean # categorical values std # categorical values total # categorical values kurtosis min kurtosis max kurtosis mean kurtosis std skewness min skewness max skewness mean skewness std <p>PCA metafeatures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> pca 95% pca skewness first pc pca kurtosis first pc <p>Landmarking metafeatures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> One Nearest Neighbor Linear Discriminant Analysis Naive Bayes Decision Tree Decision Node Learner Random Node Learner
--	--

Figure 28: Steps of the algorithm selection tool

Note that the proposed the model selection algorithm can be used for any setting: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning, self-supervised, offline learning, and online learning.

3.3 Tool overview

As shown in Figure 28, the tool offers the following functionalities:

- **User Datasets & Metrics (Input):** The process begins with the user providing their data. This can be in multiple formats, such as a CSV file, a file containing pre-calculated data metrics, or raw data in JSON format.
- **Manual Data Splitting:** The user is required to manually organize their input data into three distinct logical groups:
 - **Reference Dataset:** This is the primary dataset for which the user wants algorithm recommendations. It is the new, unseen data that needs to be analysed.
 - **Comparison Datasets:** This is a collection of historical or known datasets that will be used as a basis for comparison against the Reference Dataset.
 - **Performance Metrics of Comparison Datasets:** This is a separate file or set of data that contains information about how well different ML algorithms (like Linear Regression, Decision Trees, etc.) have performed on the Comparison Datasets in the past.
- **Data Upload:** Each of these three data objects (Reference, Comparison, Performance Metrics) is then uploaded into the system. The user has two distinct methods for this upload:
- **Upload to Interface:** This is a temporary, one-time upload. The data is stored only in the system's memory for the current session and will be discarded afterward. This is useful for quick, ad-hoc analyses.
- **Upload to Local Database:** This is a persistent upload. The data is saved to a database, making it reusable for future comparisons without needing to be uploaded again. This is ideal for building a permanent repository of comparison datasets.
- **Task Selection:** After the data is successfully uploaded using one of the two methods, the final step for the user is to specify the type of machine learning problem they are trying to solve. They select a 'task type', such as Classification or Regression. This selection is crucial as it determines which similarity metrics and performance results are relevant for the analysis.

In essence, the flowchart describes a flexible data ingestion process that allows users to either perform a quick, temporary comparison or contribute to a persistent, growing knowledge base of datasets and their associated algorithm performances.

* Performance results from training on various algorithms e.g. Linear Regression, Decision Trees etc.

Figure 29: Meta learning workflow

Figure 30 (left) shows that "Accuracy" is selected. The system displays a ranked list of similar datasets, starting with "ds4 (most similar dataset)". For this dataset, the table of algorithms is sorted in

descending order by the Accuracy column, which is highlighted to visually confirm the sorting criterion. This allows the user to quickly identify that Neural Networks and Gradient Boosting are the top performers based on overall correctness. On the right, the user has changed the dropdown selection to "Precision". The interface instantly re-ranks the algorithm table for the same dataset ("ds4"). Now, the Precision column is highlighted, and the list is re-sorted to show that Neural Networks and Gradient Boosting also have the highest precision.

In summary, this display provides an interactive and user-friendly way to explore the results, allowing users to dynamically re-order the algorithm recommendations based on the performance metric that is most important for their specific use case.

Figure 30: Meta learning example output

4 Model Deployment

ExtremeXP as an execution engine is tailoring to extreme quantities of data for experimentation purposes. A core task is to also enable the usage of data and related data to create higher performing experiments. This data may be distributed or confined under constraints of the data owners or multiple data owners. The data can be distributed to various reasons. The data owners may host their data in various cloud providers or on their own premises. The constraints of the data owners may not grant them permission to utilize the ExtremeXP framework. Or possibly the data is stored on multiple data storage platforms in the cloud whereby physical integration may not be computationally viable for the purpose of large-scale experimentation. For scaling the models that can fully utilize the potential of the experimentation engine.

The primary reason for this is the protection and ownership of the data. This imposes a significant constraint on the usage of the experimentation engine. Leading to a gap in the analytical results. We thus want to propose a solution that can allow users to perform the experimentation. The ability to conduct the experimentation will thus enable the user to achieve greater results than previously.

We propose the distribution of the architecture of machine learning models. As traditionally with a single execution environment the data would be used to fit the entire model. Meaning that the model itself will be a monolith. However, in a multi-cloud scenario, the model will need to be distributed. The change in the architecture can lead to somewhat different results. We justify our proposal through experimentation and using the consistency of results as compared to the monolith model. We have evaluated the effects of distributing various types of the models based on the analytical task. Along with the effects on further downstream analytical tasks. The results so far have been consistent with the original architectures.

We focus primarily on the task of experimenting with a classification model through the usage of various use-cases. However, our work is not limited to only classification tasks. Our work can also be utilized in conjunction with various other analytical components. The requirements for each analytical component may be different, such as the requirements for data augmentation compared to only classification or regression.

4.1 Research contribution

We conducted our research on general use-cases with distributed data. With respect to the ExtremeXP use cases, we conducted experimentation centred around use case 2 (UC2). We discuss how we distributed the training of the architecture of the machine learning models of our choice. We evaluate the results by comparing the results of the centralized model.

4.1.1 Data flow

The dataset provided by the cyber-security use-case can be considered via the different modes from which the data is collected. In this setting, each data collector would have to worry about the data's security and thus will not allow different data collectors to gain access to the data to materialize it. However, the relations between the entities of the data are known. This means that we can integrate the data if we have access to it.

The data within the UC2 dataset concerns various features collected regarding different aspects of the network. The main features collected are the HTTP, DNS, SMTP, SSL, and user information. There are also use-id and timestamps being collected for the activities. We can hypothesize that the data regarding different aspects of the network may have been collected by different parties thus are under different ownership. However, the user information and timestamps on data collection are the same. This information can be utilized to perform data integration upon aggregation.

The raw data may not be fully divulged to the external execution engine due to constraints on the data owner. The raw informative data will not leave the respective data store of the data owners. The user can define the type of data that they have and the task that they want to perform. Continuing with UC2 as an example, we can define the type of data and the task. The task for UC2 is classification. The type of data can be differentiated as multi-dimensional timeseries or as tabular data. Defining the task and type of data can define the subset of analytical models that should be utilized.

The type of data will need to be used along with the data metadata. Informative metadata that we will need to use are the extra metadata that will elevate the data from tabular to a different mode. For example, the sequential metadata that differentiates time series data with tabular data. This however is not limited to only the sequential metadata.

Another determining factor can be the budget for computing that the user can provide. This budget can determine the type of model that is recommended to use. The computational cost can vary for the training of the encoder-decoder pair. This will impact the architecture. Based on the resources available, we can dictate the architecture we and the dimensionality of the encoder-decoder pair. This is reflected to the user and can impact the downstream task. We have demonstrated this through the usage of UC2 data and varying architectures. Along with varying downstream models.

4.1.2 Architecture

Each party will be trusted to perform some local compute to pre-train an encoder model. As the data within the use-case are various time series data for each user and the goal is to perform classification. We can encode the time series using various methods. Each of these methods are a variability point for the experimentation. For example, the pre-training of time-series models some choices are autoencoders, variational autoencoders or recurrent neural network autoencoders, but are not limited to these.

The individual data owner can thus compute the output of these encoder models and transfer the intermediate representation to the execution engine to train the machine learning model. The model that can be considered can depend on the type of encoding that each data owner pre-trained. The model that each user will train-can be dependent on the local compute that each user has available. In the figure below, the encoder and decoder models do not need to be the full models used in various proven ML architectures. The output of the encoder only needs to be sufficiently different from the raw data to be able to be transported off their respective clouds onto the ExtremeXP execution engine.

Figure 31: Encoder-decoder based architecture

This means that we can recommend the usage of a very shallow encoder-decoder architecture on the client's side. Using the result of the coarse encoder, we can continue training a more fine-grained encoder-decoder network to produce the model that the experiments will be run with.

The classifiers will be trained and inferred on the experimentation framework. Encoding vectors can be transferred to the experimentation engine. For the specific cyber-security use-case this model will be a binary classifier. However, the model that the experimentation framework trains is not limited to binary classifiers, but many more. As any machine learning model that utilizes an encoder-decoder operation can be thus separated for a privacy preserving use of the experimental framework.

There is a significant difference in the utilization of our architecture and the monolith machine learning architecture. The difference being that the monolith encoder-decoder architecture is fitted on the entire dataset. Our models will be fitted on a subset of the data. In comparison, the monolith architecture will have full matrices as weights. In our proposed architectures, the weights of the model become block-diagonal. This will be natural, due to the compute of independent data owners. We thus verify that this does not significantly impact the results using various models.

4.1.3 Evaluation

We evaluated the architecture using a suite of machine learning models. The models that we primarily evaluate using are some widely used machine learning models for classification. The models we selected are Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and gradient boosted trees (XGBoost). We focus our evaluation primarily on classification because the task of the dataset is binary classification. The evaluation that we performed are the comparison between the performance of the models.

Conducting experiments on the data from use-case 2, Cyber Security, we can obtain the below results. We can realize the fact that the results do not deviate from the norm meaning that the different architectures can provide very similar results for the current state of the data. However, the different architectures of the machine learning models can allow different users to perform experiments.

ARCHITECTURE	MODEL	ACCURACY
Standard	LSTM	0.98657
Stacked	LSTM-LSTM	0.98657
Stacked	AE – LSTM	0.97986
Distributed	LSTM-XGB	0.98657
Distributed	LSTM-RF	0.98657
Distributed	LSTM-LR	0.98657
Stacked	LSTM-XGB	0.98657
Stacked	LSTM-RF	0.98657
Stacked	LSTM-LR	0.98657

Table 15: Results of Different Architectures

To evaluate the stacked architecture, the model is given as follows. The user side pretrained model used are an autoencoder and LSTM-autoencoder. Given the different encoder-decoder models, the intermediate embeddings are different. The difference in representation also indicates the different machine learning models that can be utilized. The main difference being the classifier that can be immediately utilized for experimentation.

For various data settings, we can also perform the experimentation. Depending on the number of data sources, the operations performed at the server-side will be different. If there is only a single data source, the intermediate data that is received can be immediately used. If there are multiple data sources, then an aggregation of the data needs to occur. We assume that the data from each individual data source are independent, thus we will concatenate them with each other along the vertical axis. The post-concatenation data can thus be used for training the model.

For the baseline of the centralized setting to differentiate the models, we utilize a LSTM classifier. As, if we use the LSTM as part of an encoder-decoder architecture, then the model architecture will be the same as in the stacked case. As the encoder-decoder will need to undergo pretraining. For the data scenario with multiple data sources, a federated approach can be utilized. Each party can independently train an encoder-decoder model, and the experimental framework will provide the aggregation for the machine learning model as seen in Figure 32: Example Architecture for Multi-Cloud.

Figure 32: Example Architecture for Multi-Cloud

The above illustration can allow us to fully utilize the distributed data. The proposed encoder-decoder networks can be differentiated given the constraints. Such as the architecture of the encoder-decoder (autoencoder) layer in the model on the client side. As the different autoencoder networks require varied quantity of compute.

Security Guarantee

Given that the data are from different cloud storages, we can also provide some privacy guarantees of the data. Providing the original data never leaves the storage, the privacy of the data will be preserved. This is a significant constraint in terms of the usage of multiple sources of storage. This means that we need to guarantee that for the sake of the data owners, that the transference of the representations of the data will not decrease the security of the raw data itself. We thus have a guarantee of the preservation of this constraint while using the above architecture.

To do this we utilize a very simple definition of a valid function. A function here being the autoencoder. For this function to be valid there needs to be a domain, and a codomain and a mapping between these two sets. The computation of the encoder will be the mapping. The codomain is the vector space of the output of the encoder.

In our setting, the security of the data is primarily on the user side to protect against possible leakage to others through the experimentation engine(server). However, from the point of view of the server to perform a valid attack on the data two out of the three components need to be accessible, i.e. either the domain and codomain is accessible or the domain and mapping, or mapping and codomain. However, in our proposed architecture only the codomain is accessible thus meaning that the raw data will be secure and safe.

4.1.4 Model Deployment

We propose that to enable users to utilize the ExtremeXP experimentation framework, to have two sides of operations for deployment. The two sides being server-side and client-side. We propose that the recommendation of the variability points can also be proposed for either side of the functionalities. On the client side, we would recommend the user to select the type of encoder-decoder architecture they want to employ. The complexity or computation requirement would depend on the mode of data that the user has.

4.2 Variability Points

Our tool allows users to adjust the following parameters, which depend on both the model being evaluated and the dataset itself.

Model Choice

- **Description:** These are the model with which the algorithm was evaluated with. These models themselves have a set of hyper-parameters that can be set depending on the exact model that needs to be evaluated against.
- **Options:** linear regression, logistic regression, K-nearest neighbours (KNN), K-means, decision trees, random forests, gradient boosting trees.

Encoder Choice

- **Description:** These are the architectures that can be used for the autoencoder architecture. These are primarily neural models but can be pre-trained and are task dependent. The type of architecture will be specific to the type of data and type of task.
- **Considerations:** we can consider are to also select an encoder function based on the cost. The cost being the computational budget that the user is willing to provide themselves in conjunction to using the ExtremeXP framework.
- **Options:** Autoencoder, Variational Autoencoder, LSTM-autoencoder, etc.

5 Conclusion

This deliverable covered the research activities related T3.4, T3.5 and T3.6. In all these tasks, very good results have been obtained showing the successful execution of the tasks. In fact, some related KPIs related to the performance of the resulting algorithms (see Table 16: Progress on relevant KPIs) show the quality of the outcome.

Overall, several algorithms have resulted from the work executed. The investigations were driven by the type of constraints which mostly consisted of (1) reducing the number of false positives/false negatives in imbalanced data and 2) increase clustering quality for high-dimensional data and 3) embedding physics-related information in ML. This highlights quite clearly the rich setup and context of the work conducted which has been mostly informed by the use cases. More investigative work on other types of constraints could be beneficial for ExtremeXP. On the other hand, the continual and online learning were studied, but not extensively to the extent that all offline algorithms have been adapted to operate online. More work should be dedicated to this aspect. Moreover, the model recommendation using meta-learning is a good piece of work and could be extended to cover more datasets similarity measures to fit different types of data like images and time series.

The proposed algorithms need to be evaluated on other benchmarks beyond the use cases, and this is currently ongoing which will help contribute to a few publications that are being prepared. Some publications are already out (like the work done on clustering which was mostly done independently of any of the use cases). Over the coming period, if time allows, we will consider the following actions:

- Evaluation of UEC on use cases data
- Evaluation of the proposed algorithms on other benchmarks
- Submit all outstanding studies as papers to journals/conferences
- Clean the code and disclose it as open-source code
- Explore other types of constraints

In conclusion, the work undertaken in this WP meets the initial plan, showing both originality and quality. The resulting outcome clearly supports the ExtremeXP framework about user-defined constraints, continual update of the models and their systematic recommendation in presence of new experiments on unknown and new datasets.

KPI	Description and target	Progress
3.1	Increase of accuracy of algorithm by at least 10% compared to the state-of-the-art methods.	<p>Accuracy is an unreliable metric for imbalanced datasets, as a model can achieve a high score by simply predicting the majority class. For instance, a model classifying all traffic as "benign" in a dataset with 5% malicious traffic would be 95% accurate but useless for security.</p> <p>A more robust measure is the F1-score, which is the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall. This single metric provides a balanced assessment of a model's performance by considering both critical error types:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • False Negatives (missed threats): A low False Negative Rate (FNR) corresponds to high Recall. • False Positives (false alarms): A low False Positive Rate (FPR) corresponds to high Precision. <p>A high F1-score requires a model to minimize both missed threats and false alarms simultaneously, it serves as a much more sensible and comprehensive measure of accuracy for security applications.</p> <p>In offline scenario, we set BCE as baseline. All, except one, hybrid algorithms achieve over 10% improvement on F-score. HAROW being the best algorithm.</p> <p>In streaming scenario, we consider OPA as baselines. OGCL shows F-score improvement of well over 10% in all datasets except Phishing smartphone. Furthermore, OGCL achieves the best F-score on all datasets.</p>
3.2	Steady increase of precision of the selection strategies because of continual learning.	<p>The meta-learning tool example is to show a constant evaluation of strategies and promotion of the ones that perform best on some pre-defined criteria.</p> <p>Imagine we want the algorithm with the lowest false alarms on the Crypto desktop dataset.</p> <p>Static Approach: We sort our database, find that "Algorithm A" had the lowest false alarms historically, and deploy it. We are now blind to its future performance.</p> <p>Continual Learning Approach: We deploy a set of algorithms. In the first hour, "Algorithm A" performs well, so the system relies on it. But in the second hour, scenario changes, and "Algorithm A" starts generating many false alarms. The system instantly penalizes it. Simultaneously, it notices that "Algorithm B," which was quiet before, is now perfectly accurate. The system dynamically shifts its trust to "Algorithm B."</p> <p>The result is that the system's overall precision increases, not because it picked the right strategy from the start, but because it learned to abandon a failing strategy and adopt a winning one.</p>
3.6	Decrease the manual work of ML engineers for deployment.	<p>We performed experimentation on the datasets for UC2 (cyber security) on the task of classification. We have also conducted the study of the utilization and distribution of the data to use various partitions.</p> <p>Approach: We provide the executable model. The ML engineer can perform low-cost fine-tuning. Our work with very low-cost local compute will enable more optimal usage of the extremeXP framework in analytical tasks.</p>

		Baseline: The execution and experimentation allow us to verify that the result of the experimentation does not degrade significantly when we perform the operations with our changed architecture. There is no significant or any loss between the distributed and mono.
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Table 16: Progress on relevant KPIs

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